

**USING NARRATIVE AND ARTS-BASED METHODS TO
MAKE VISIBLE (DRAW OUT) LEARNING IN SECONDARY
ART EDUCATION**

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Cognisant of the ongoing tensions that exist within the academy and especially within Schools of Education concerning the use of 'arts-based' and 'narrative inquiry' methods, my approach to doctoral study set out to both satisfy and disrupt the dissertation requirements at my institution. I'm therefore grateful for the opportunity and support shown by my UWS supervisors Dr Anne Pirrie and Dr Stephen Day. I must also express my profound thanks to Dr Malcolm Reed of the University of Bristol where the initial thinking for this thesis was first advanced. Thanks too must go to my students who have endured my persistent questioning of art's pedagogy. A final thanks to KLVM for all the love and support.

Abstract

The purpose of this research as the thesis title suggests was to make learning visible through arts practice in secondary art education and by extension make theory and the process of reflection more accessible to secondary aged pupils as well as others including post graduate students.

Pupils' perceived inability to articulate their learning in art along with the high failure rate of the Scottish Qualifications Authority (SQA) National 5 exam 'question paper' are the issues which gave rise to much of the impetus for this study.

The research aims were to identify, through conversations and ethnographic observations of participants' arts-practice, how learners come to know, understand, and articulate their own learning in the art and design classroom. By adopting a practice of 'staring' (Speedy, 2015) as one of the research methods, this helped the process of 'noticing' and 'paying attention' in the data gathering stage of the research. I ask what does learning look like for 14 pupils from across secondary 1-6 (12-18 years old) in a Scottish secondary school art department. To find out this professional doctorate invoked both arts-based and narrative inquiry methods, to ask the following questions: how do secondary school pupils in art and design develop knowledge and skills in arts practice? What value do pupils place on the knowledge and skills developed in arts practice? And to what extent do current assessment practices encourage pupils to fully account for their learning in art and design?

This study sheds new light on concepts like the irreducible and ineffable qualities of art in education. It highlights the power of unknowing to ignite a pedagogy of learning that moves cognitive levels from the normative to the critical. This understanding may also open new avenues to explore how art can be such a potent medium for understanding reality, for self-knowledge, liberation, pleasure, discipline, and the exercise of power.

And finally, the thesis offers a new way of reading this reality vis-à-vis the case study assemblage where I adopt what Fernando Hernandez-Hernandez (2019:60) refers to as the *pedagogical imagination* to 'afford us the capacity to create, isolated from routines and trends'.

Keywords

Art and Design; Arts Practice; Arts-Based Methods; Case Study Assemblage; Critical Pedagogy; Unknowing; Narrative Inquiry; Scottish Teacher Education; Secondary Art Teacher Education, Professional Reflection.

CHAPTER 1

INTRODUCTION

This study will seek to identify, through conversations and ethnographic observations of participants' arts-practice, how learners come to know, understand and articulate their own learning in the art and design classroom

Making theory 'accessible through arts practice' is a central concern of the work of this thesis. Positioning 'arts practice' as the conduit for this making is important to me as an artist, educator, and researcher. Through utilising 'arts practice' I can interrogate the field of study and generate a more fulsome and useful pedagogical narrative.

In understanding this Professional Doctorate, I have explored and critiqued more broadly my own sense of identity as an Artist and Professional Educator (see page 6.)

Mishler's 'critical analytic perspective' on narrative theory provided 'ways of telling' in interviewing that were key to the insight I gained into my research participants (Mishler, 2004:50). The power of the interview in opening-up a multi-layered discussion with pupils on art in education is there to see in the assemblages.

That grip of Mishler's methods as outlined in his *Storylines* (2004) offered me a framework for 'noticing' and 'paying attention' that has helped me to 'see' myself as a both social scientist and art educator.

These multiple identities have allowed me to harness the sustainable pedagogical benefits of unknowing, and to resist where possible the quest for certainty.

Pupils' perceived inability to articulate their learning in art along with the high failure rate of the National 5 exam 'question paper' for the Scottish Qualifications Authority (SQA) are the main reasons I decided this would make a worthy research topic as a

Professional Doctorate . It felt as though this was a concern that needed to be worked through and made visible as they have been in the ‘assemblages’.

Staring, as a method of reflection (and research) has long been part of the art studio setting — it is a practice I use when I stop to evaluate what has been achieved in the studio or art-class following a period of art making. Jane Speedy (2015) in her poetic autoethnographic inquiry *Staring at the Park* adopted staring as a research methodology following a stroke which limited her physical mobility thus leaving the park outside her flat window her only view on the outside world. Indeed, I know, too, of ‘*staring’s*’ significance to film. One only needs to think of Hitchcock’s (1954) *Rear Window* for a classic portrayal of the power of staring, where James Stewart, the protagonist of the story, is confined to his apartment due to an accident, is left with his rear window as his only portal to the outside world. Yet, the usefulness of the methodology of ‘staring’ in educational research is far from settled. Staring at photographs though is commonplace in our world today and is often used to help us draw down the most powerful of memories — an observation that is advanced here later when pupils who participated in this research are asked to recall their art learning as part of this Professional Doctorate.

Fig. 1 Ivan Illich at Corofin Village Hall (May,1989) (Photo: courtesy of Michael Neylon) Permission to reproduce images given by Michael Neylon.

The image in Fig. 1, depicts Ivan Illich (May,1989) and like other images throughout this dissertation, contains bodies of knowledge (Rose, 2016) which are set in time and place. By hanging out with or staring at these images I experience again the evocations of that time and place. Thirty years on from that formative experience which altered the course of my career and *I’m* back in *that* village hall in Corofin listening again to Ivan Illich. Illich continues to remain prescient with numerous recent publications reminding us of his continued relevance within educational discourse (Gabbard, 2019; O’Donovan, 2010; Baldacchino, 2020).

Illich, defies characterisation with his wide-ranging views on medicine (*Medical Nemesis*, 1974), literacy and more generally schooling, most notably his publication *De-schooling Society* (1971), his best-known which questioned the very institution of the school and what schools *should* be.

This gathering in Corofin was organised by campaigners for 'alternatives in education' of which I considered myself one, and they drew inspiration from *De-schooling Society* (1971), (O'Donovan, 2010).

While a painting or a prose description can never be anything other than a selective interpretation (Sontag, 1978), a photograph is, according to Sontag, '...a privileged moment, turned into a slim object that one can keep and look at again' (Sontag 1978:18).

Hence, on a clear and bright May evening in 1989 (I was 23) I was fortunate to be part of this public gathering with Illich. Ivan Illich had come to the village of Corofin in the West of Ireland at the invitation of the neighbouring co-operative school known as *the Shed* (Fig. 2). He came to engage with and support those involved in the school and since I was involved (albeit on the periphery) I, too, got to experience and 'own' the debate that followed that evening.

De-schooling the curriculum, collapsing and rebuilding the infrastructure around education, questioning ideas of schooling and considering how best to organise it pedagogically and rebuilding it for today's society was front and centre of the debate that evening. A comparable debate for today might well be how we 'decolonise the curriculum' which is currently underway in the UK as schools attempt to acknowledge and rid education of its links to slavery and colonisation.

The memory and sheer hope that that occasion offered, signified here by that image of Illich (Fig. 1), remains seminal to my early development as an educator and researcher and continues to resonate and guide my pedagogical trajectory today.

Equally resonant is the image of the Room 13 studio, in Fort William (Fig. 3). This studio had become my spiritual home over the course of the last decade or so and was host to several critical pedagogy seminars on art education which I organised and where many of the ideas in this thesis were first explored and contested, such

as the concept of 'studio thinking' as developed by Hetland, et al (2013) to be explored later in the thesis.

The examples above highlight the point that images can be as powerful as text in communicating concepts and experiences (Rose, 2016). With this in mind, in this dissertation, the reader is challenged to *read* both the image and text with the same care and attention, affording each mode the same privilege and authority. These are the demands presented by the reading of a visual essay to which this dissertation aligns (Sousanis, 2015).

Fig. 2 The Shed Cooperative School and Studio, Roxton, Corofin, circa 2010
(Photo: courtesy of Deirdre O' Mahony)

Permission to reproduce figure granted by Dr. Deirdre O' Mahony on 23/01/2023.

Fig. 3 Room 13 Studio at Caol Primary, Fort William, circa 2013,
(Photo: courtesy of Room 13 International)

The following questions make up the research aims.

- How do secondary school pupils in art and design (henceforth, pupils) develop knowledge and skills in arts practice?
- What value do pupils place on the knowledge and skills developed in arts practice?
- To what extent do current assessment practices encourage pupils to fully account for their learning in art and design?

The research objectives are:

- To capture learning conversations around arts-practice in the secondary phase of school through an ethnographic approach using narrative and arts-based methods that can inform teacher pedagogy and curriculum design.
- To develop (using arts-based and narrative methods) a pedagogical method that makes visible and provides access to areas of art and design learning that is difficult to verbally articulate.

SELF-REFLECTIONS ON THE DPROF - THE JOURNEY TOWARDS A PROFESSIONAL DOCTORATE

I'm writing this (wee) narrative *about the researcher* after some considerable time in academia pursuing my doctorate. In the process of writing this thesis it became evident that as I reviewed and reflected I had completely forgotten to adequately address the person at the centre of this study, the arbitrator of everything and the person to benefit most from the study *myself* and whilst I do refer to myself throughout the thesis, I had managed to reveal very little of who I was way back at the start of this research journey and who I am now as I conclude this DProf journey.

You will have noticed above that I bracketed the word 'wee' simply because this is a word which was not part of my vocabulary prior to securing my current academic position in Scotland for which I have held for seventeen years.

In the late 1990's I moved to the UK from Ireland to pursue a higher degree in art education at the University of Warwick, as the precise degree that I was seeking to do did not exist in Ireland at the time, it does now! Prior to this I was very content with my life in Dublin, I taught art three days a week at a state secondary school (St Kevin's College in Crumlin on Dublin's Southside) and spent the remaining part of the week in my studio on Henrietta Street in Dublin's North inner city. I spent four years in that city honing my skills as an artist-teacher. By then I had achieved some success in both teaching and in my studio output which allowed me the time to pause and consider my options which eventually led me to the UK.

This move was made possible having received a scholarship (*Arts Educators Award* for post graduate study) from the Arts Council of Ireland which financed the costs of my MA in Art and Design Education. Had I not embarked upon this MA degree and not lost myself in the university for a year reading Kant, Wittgenstein and other philosophical texts I might not have made such a purposeful arrival at doctoral studies all those years later. The pathway to doctoral studies was indirect, perhaps it was always intended that way, and I lost my way on countless occasions. Looking back now at my route to doctoral qualification it all seemed mapped out but on

reflection who would plan for years of difficult thinking that constantly questioned your identity? That's it there, the doctoral process summed up!

I am now the subject lead for secondary art and design teacher education at the University of the West of Scotland (UWS) having established its professional graduate diploma in art education (PGDE) seventeen years ago. Prior to this I had taught on a post-graduate certificate art teacher education course (PGCE) at the University of Exeter and before that worked as an art teacher at various secondary schools both in the UK and in Ireland.

Establishing Scotland's first 'Artist Teacher' Master of Education programme over ten years ago at UWS in collaboration with Glasgow Museums and then developing an association with the Glasgow International (GI) festival of contemporary art meant I had immediate access to all the necessary professional, creative and intellectual challenge in which to fully develop as an artist teacher researcher. Embarking in doctoral research at the University of Bristol in 2014 afforded me another extended period of deep professional reflection this time reading for Narrative Inquiry and Visual Methods over a series of seven modules which served as the pre-module stages for the Professional Doctorate (see *Appendix 1* for a full account)

At around this time I also founded the Network of Art Teachers Across Scotland (NATAS), a professional network for art teachers in Scotland which meant I had an audience with which to engage with.

The notion that contemporary art raises 'contemporary issues' – the latter issue being a curriculum theme within Scottish Education gripped me and sustained my academic enquiry for several years including my advisory work with ENGAGE¹ I then developed a critical pedagogical seminar that ran as part of the GI festival. I felt I had finally 'arrived' professionally and was now also beginning to publish on Scottish education. Recent publications include a contribution in the SAGE

1

Engage are the leading charity in the UK for promoting engagement and participation in the visual arts. Engage is supported in Scotland by Creative Scotland.

Handbook of Critical Pedagogies (Jeffery and McAuliffe, 2020) and in Scottish Education (5th Ed) (McAuliffe, 2018) from Edinburgh University Press.

I have conducted Creative Scotland funded research with my colleague GJ on the viability of drawing, walking, and extending sites for learning as heuristic tools in curriculum design and professional reflection. I now identify as an artist-teacher-researcher and over the course of time, beginning in the studio, and then into the classroom and back into the studio again this identity has strengthened. The framing of that tripartite identity now sits comfortably with who I think I have become following this complex and at times challenging process of Professional Doctorate study.

In the Chapters that follow I explore in Chapter 2 the hegemony of text-based approaches to learning and how this is manifest through-out state schooling in Scotland. I position the ineffable and tentative and argue for their consideration in the assessment of art.

In Chapter 3 I outline the research story from design to analysis. I offer a rationale for choosing Case study method and deal with the various ethical issues I encountered conducting this research. In Chapter 4, I explain how I constructed the 'assemblages' and why I chose this method to enable pupil voice. In Chapter 5, I present the fourteen Case Study Assemblages in a 'gallery' format, free of explanatory text to privilege their artful dimensions. In Chapter 6 I demonstrate the appropriateness of using concept visualisation for professional reflection on the secondary art course and show how the methods developed to produce the 'assemblages' can also be applied to other learning settings, such as the case of the South Asian teachers using 'concept visualisation' to unpack an academic paper. In the final chapter, Chapter 7, I make the following policy recommendations and draw the thesis to a close.

1. Rebalancing the image/text hierarchy in education
2. Dismantling Frameworks of Dominance in Scottish art education
3. Reinstating Cognition: studio thinking, latency, unknowing and deep learning.
4. Interdisciplinarity: Reframing the Dialogue between Arts and Sciences
5. Teachers as Curriculum Developers and Change Agents

The policy recommendations that I have listed above and expanded upon in Chapter 7, could not all have been anticipated at the beginning of the research. The coronavirus pandemic had not yet happened and the subsequent 'fall-out' this had on the SQA National art and design assessments was still to unfold. The Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) had not yet published their damning review of *Curriculum for Excellence: Into the Future* (OECD, 2021) and the impact this would have on the future of the SQA.

CHAPTER 2

THE OBJECT OF THE INQUIRY

Fig.4 and Fig. 5: Stills from a video performance: I'm going to do what I normally do, EVA International Biennial of Contemporary Art, 1999 (McAuliffe, 1999)
 Permission to reproduce figures granted by EVA International Biennial of Contemporary Art.

To unlearn, I must get uncomfortable. To do this, I take the vein of curiosity and pleasure in my creative practice; my comfort in which I hold myself steady and mediate, and I must slice it open. I rupture. Smudge. Smear. Wipe it away. (McLeod, 2020: 5)

Like artworks, research and scholarly texts do not typically reveal themselves spontaneously but need to be attended to carefully so that things that we would ordinarily miss during a quick first read or with first glance would not go unseen. (O'Donoghue, 2020: 61.3 192)

This study will seek to identify, through conversations with and ethnographic observations of participants' arts-practice, how learners come to know, understand and articulate their own learning in the art and design classroom. Figs. 4 and 5 come from a series of still images from the seminal performance *I'm going to do what I normally do* (McAuliffe, 1999). This performance bolstered my interest in pedagogical inquiry. Using arts-based methods (Sullivan, 2010; Leavy, 2019; Sinner, Irwin and Adams, 2019) the performance attempted a dialogue between art, music making and mathematical inquiry. The performance operated on many levels but chiefly it was the start of an aesthetic dialogue between academic subjects which 'troubled' how pedagogy is conceived and 'curricularised' (Baldacchino, 2020; Hernandez-Hernandez, 2019; Ilich, 1971).

The following study is part of that continuum. It finds general agreement with Baldacchino and Justice (2019: 4) when they argue that 'art seems to move forward when it loses its way' and is allowed flow. Shakespeare put it another way in *Hamlet* when he stated that 'by indirection we find direction out' (Shakespeare, 1609/2020). To make gains in a creative field, we need to be prepared to lose our way and even 'wipe it away' (McLeod, 2020), and in some cases begin again. In other words, we need to trouble or disrupt the normative ways of thinking and making. This process of erasure is high stakes for a working 'creative' and potentially very challenging and even devastating for a secondary school pupil who needs to finish their art project within certain timescales and to a prescribed format. This leaves little room to consider 'wip[ing] it away' (McLeod et al, 2020: 5).

It is critical therefore to the reading of the thesis that we acknowledge the performative aspects of the art-making, namely the *case study assemblages* that are

central to this thesis (Spry, 2001; Bal, 2003; Shields and Irwin 2019). Whilst the case study assemblages (an example can be seen in Fig. 6) are meant to provoke deep pedagogical thinking they also 'set... up an open-ended, ambiguous and imaginative space for research' (McLeod et al, 2020: 253) providing an alternative to the written word (Sousanis, 2015). They provide significant epistemological insights into how the participants in the study came to know, understand and articulate their own learning in the art-room, particularly in light of the challenges they faced in verbal expression.

The pupils were invited to engage in a process of reflection on the art and design work they had produced to fulfil the course criteria of whatever course of study they were enrolled on, be it Broad General Education (BGE), National 5 (N5) or Higher. The pupils were asked to respond to a number of questions (9 in total) set out in Appendix 2.

The responses to these questions, which were audio recorded and transcribed, along with work-in progress images and in some cases personal statements relating to a student's project, were brought together using the technique of collage and superimposition with the aid of photoshop to form a single unified image, forming a record of the student's art learning. These artefacts are described as *Case Study Assemblages* throughout this thesis.

1.0 Can you describe what you are doing right now?
 I am currently doing national five art and design and I'm doing expressive right now I'm working up to creating my final piece which will be still life.

1.1 Can you talk me through your process of your art-making? (have you made this?)
 So this is a single object - this is a polaroid camera what is my theme is my favourite things. So I have collated some of my favourite things relating to what I'm doing and so I really like photography. And my camera is my project. And how have you made this picture? Generally when I start drawing I like to split my picture into four sections and I work in sections. Is there an original photograph that replicates this?
 So you chose to isolate the rest of it and cut out this? So the picture was taken of the single object.

1.2 What was the most difficult aspect of your making?
 I think making it the same shape ... are

1.3 What was the least difficult aspect?
 Probably adding the tone.

1.4 What do you hope to learn by making this? (What is the range of knowledge and skills in arts practice?)
 And Maybe further improve my tone pencil skills.

1.5 What knowledge and skills do you hope to achieve?

1.6 What knowledge and skills are valued by you?
 Fashion Design Course

1.7 What knowledge and skills are valued by the school?
 Model

1.8 Do you have the subject-specific language to enable you to verbally articulate your learning?
 Textiles

1.9 Do learners need to be able to describe their learning (in verbal and written modes) and if so what are the benefits?
 Learning

I'm quite a perfectionist

Female Torso

Fig. 6 Case Study Assemblage No. X

Amira

Fig. 7 Amira's display boards and evaluations being prepared for presentation for N5 Art and Design (a)

Fig. 8 Amira's display boards being prepared for presentation for N5 Art and Design (b)

The assemblage is made up of various aspects of the student's portfolio in both Art and Design (Expressive and Design) together with evaluative statements (as seen in Fig. 7 and Fig. 8). Fig. 6 displays the completed assemblage which includes the interview schedule along with the student's responses to the research questions

(these have been superimposed on top of the course work enabling the research question to be considered whilst 'staring' at the completed course work). This is an educative device that is being tested here to see if it helps pupils to consider their making and thinking in both written and visual form in the same space.

This study proposes that we should build into the art educational fabric at school level a greater tolerance and value for the ineffable, for hesitation and tentativeness when attending to the art making process. It is this careful durational attention that 'reveals the previously 'unseen' (O'Donoghue, 2020). That 'unseen' or unknowable element is often the very essence of creativity.

Baldacchino (2019: 10) asks in his book on 'unlearning' whether art can be taught. His answer is yes, with the caveat that 'art must not be learnt'. This reply captures the substance and difficulty contained in such an everyday question as it implies that, for art to remain art, its outcomes must not be fixed or overly determined. An element of the 'unknown' must therefore be maintained (Atkinson, 2018; Fisher and Fortnum, 2008). The Scottish *Curriculum for Excellence* (CfE) places a lot of emphasis on determining lesson outcomes in advance. This does not sit well with the creative process, where to determine the outcome in advance is to negate the purpose of the lesson, which is to learn as one goes along. To learn to live with 'not knowing' and 'losing our way' is essential to this journey (Atkinson 2018; Baldacchino, 2019; McLeod, 2020).

In this vein, this study sought to identify, through a series of conversations with learners (14 in total; 7 male and 7 female; aged 13-18 years) and ethnographic observations (Mishler, 1999) of participants' arts-practice, how pupils come to know, understand and articulate their own learning.

Using narrative and arts-based methods, the study sought to locate and capture learner conversations about secondary art and design learning in and through the research participants' (the pupils') own art and design making. The learner conversations (Mishler, 1996; Reissman, 2008) were conducted over the course of one school year at key points in the development of the pupils' projects while I 'hung out' alongside them in their classrooms and observed their process in order to

develop a deeper understanding of their learning and meaning makings (Heath, 1985).

Mary Ann Stankiewicz's editorial in *Studies in Art Education* (2015) posed the question 'Why Research in Art Education?' She drew on Jerome Hausman's inaugural editorial to 'Studies' in 1959 where '...the assumption was that the more one theorized about art education, the less one was able to teach with sensitivity and understanding' (Stankiewicz, 2015: 3). Crass though it sounds, this rather commonly accepted anti-intellectual viewpoint, has, I would argue, beleaguered the subject's development before and since, and as this study will demonstrate has contributed to the intellectual impoverishment of the subject in Scottish schools. The most obvious manifestation of this phenomenon is the fact that in art education the emphasis is still on practical skills development. This focus has its origins in Scotland's industrial past when art meant craft and was on the curriculum to mainly serve industries such as engineering and shipbuilding, and creativity was not a feature of the subject (McAuliffe, 2013). Practical skills are still being promoted by the SQA to the detriment of the development of a more valuable and progressive 'ideas-based' curriculum which provides greater challenge (Humes and Priestley, 2021; McAuliffe, 2018).

The notable John Steers who served on the editorial board of *International Journal of Art and Design Education* (iJADE) from 1981 until his retirement in 2011, wrote a seminal paper in 2003 identifying a 'theory gap' in art and design education in the UK drawing on Doug Boughton's (1995) words to express the *inherent problem* as he saw it:

'(a)ny attempt to use written statements intended to describe the range of complex and subtle characteristics of visual expressive work at any level of schooling will be less than adequate...The qualitative nature of the arts ...cannot be effectively captured in words alone. Linguistic representation of arts is best reductionist, and at worst misleading' (Boughton in Steers 2003:25).

A fitting response to this situation is a more critical visual response where art-making is critical art-making and not just an exercise in demonstrating the handling of art materials. The case study assemblages presented in this thesis embody this kind of critical thinking.

THE HEGEMONY OF TEXT-BASED APPROACHES TO LEARNING

The linguistic bias or hegemony of text-based approaches to learning has given rise to what can be identified as a crisis in pupils' ability to articulate their art learning, an aspect that is evident when reading any of the assemblages. The purpose of this thesis is to find out how learners come to know, understand and articulate their own learning. We know from Clarke (2007) and others (e.g., Heath, 1985) that the language we use to talk about art learning needs to stem from the discipline itself because:

...[a]s soon as the specialist language of any professional discipline is decoded, demythologised the barrier is breached. Then the necessary use of specialist language is separated from unnecessary jargon and most pupils begin to find themselves empowered, no longer excluded from professional discourse.
(Clarke, 2007: 41)

The creeping dominance of text-based understandings has gone predominantly unchallenged across the school system in Scotland. The art teaching profession appears to have little agency around how their subject is assessed. There seems to be uncritical acceptance of text-based approaches which must be challenged to allow all forms of articulation to coexist, as, after all, we now live in a multi-modal world (Sousanis, 2015).

The written word has always had a place of privilege in educational discourse including within the field of art education. Within the last two years alone Scotland has seen a noticeable rise in pupils taking Higher Photography at the senior phase of secondary education (SQA, 2021). There are ongoing arguments around the academic value of photography as a subject, and whether it should be afforded parity with all other subjects for the purposes of university entrance remains in question. The official response from the SQA was to simply increase the written component and make Higher Photography more 'academic', thus subscribing to the afore-mentioned hegemony of text-based approaches to learning. As the text-based approaches to its assessment take hold, many pupils are now finding the 'Higher' course in Photography a challenge. The following is pertinent to this development:

'Something happens when you have to write it down. It just goes. It just closes down...I don't know. It's really reduced to something not relevant' - secondary art and design teacher 2019 (In Blunden:916, 2019).

Arguments were also advanced within concerned groups such as the Network of Art Teachers Across Scotland (NATAS) regarding pupils' articulation of their art learning. The three questions which make up the research aims of this study (see page 5) - embrace many of these anxieties.

Pupils' capacity to articulate their art learning was an area of real concern for the school in which the research was conducted, a high achieving school ranked within the top 10 in Scotland. This concern was in part triggered by a continuous series of poor SQA results in the National 5 Question Paper in which the pupils are asked to:

- respond to unseen prompts and images
- demonstrate knowledge and understanding of the impact of social, cultural and/or other influences on artists' and designers' work and practice
- demonstrate knowledge and understanding of expressive art and design elements, using appropriate art and design vocabulary

(https://www.sqa.org.uk/files_ccc/ArtAndDesignCourseSpecN5.pdf)

Further testimony to an emerging crisis in what are considered acceptable forms of assessment within art and design education is provided in the table below. This shows that the National Mean Mark for the Art and Design Question Paper in 2019 was 17.1. This result represents a fail, and every other year before and since the National 5 was introduced in 2013 the result has been similar, which means that the paper has never achieved a pass grade since it was introduced. The overall grade is built-in to the practical portfolio so no 'real' notice has been taken (Blunden, 2019), and, in turn, no remediating strategy has ever been proffered.

A	B	C	D			E			F			G			H			I			J			K			L
Code	Name	Level	Component 1			Component 2			Component 3			Name	Max Mark	Mean													
			Name	Max Mark	Mean	Name	Max Mark	Mean	Name	Max Mark	Mean																
X806 75	Accounting	National 5	Question Paper	130	85.9	Assignment	50	38.6																			
X801 75	Administration and IT	National 5	Question Paper	50	29.6	Assignment	70	43.7																			
X844 75	Applications of Mathematics	National 5	Paper 1 (Non Calculator)	45	21.8	Paper 2 (Calculator)	65	36.9																			
X804 75	Art and Design	National 5	Question Paper	50	17.1	Portfolio: Expressive	100	77.3	Portfolio: Design	100	65.1																
X807 75	Biology	National 5	Section 2	75	39.4	Section 1 - Objective Test	25	16.1	Assignment	25	15.8																

Fig. 9. Component mean marks 2019 - National Mean Marks, SQA ([https://www.sqa.org.uk/sqa/files_ccc/Component Marks 2019 National Mean Marks.xls](https://www.sqa.org.uk/sqa/files_ccc/Component_Marks_2019_National_Mean_Marks.xls)).

The question that arises from this is whether the assessment is fit for purpose and would some more meaningful multi-modal form, such as an oral examination that would focus on the pupils' own work, be more appropriate. Does it always have to default to the written word when, arguably, many pupils take up art to escape text-driven assessments?

A key finding from this research is that in order to achieve the highest grade in the subject of Art and Design in Scotland you need to be able to express yourself in written, spoken and visual form. Though the spoken word is not a form that is assessed, there is a distinct sense from the accounts of the participants in this research that, unless you can verbally describe and write down your learning, 'you are somewhat a failure', as described by Maura, a first year (S1) secondary student. Other pupils such as Lewis stated that *if you know how to speak about it, it means you really know what you are doing (sic)*. Jason, a second year (S2) student was quick to say that *a lot of things are hard to describe* and that *pupils need to be able to describe their learning*. These statements firmly point toward the hegemony of the written word and more widely text-based approaches to learning which continue to dominate the field of education.

BRUSHING AGAINST THE INEFFABLE AND THE TENTATIVE: THE ASSESSMENT OF ART IN SCOTTISH STATE SCHOOLS

Those who make art will know that *certainty* is rarely if ever a desired outcome let alone arrived at in the process of art making (Fisher and Fortnum, 2008; Hickman, 2005). For much of the time 'makers' are operating within fluid and uncertain liminal spaces between the ineffable and the tentative (Deleuze and Guattari, 1987). The 'final outcome' as it is affectionately known in Scottish art education is to all intents and purposes a very misguided reference to the completed piece of course work. The focus on the final piece disregards the pedagogical journey that a student has taken. It is in the pursuit of the 'final outcome' that pupils end up with work that is often devoid of important qualities such as subtlety and nuance and as a result the work often appears formulaic with little suggestion of the creative and vulnerable aspects that are germane to accomplished art and design making (McAuliffe 2013; 2018).

The assemblages are in effect 'works of art' — my works of art or 'pedagogical portraits' which was their initial working title for much of project before settling on the present title. These were built up or collaged around the pupils' own personal projects using a variety of arts-based methods (Leavy, 2018, Kirkpatrick et al 2021) and narrative (Mishler, 1999). These methods were used to elicit the pupils' own voices in the form of 'learner conversations' derived from their art learning and meaning making which was observed by the researcher throughout the making process. These assemblages are constructed using the pupils' own words (transcriptions) along with images from their course work at various stages in their journey towards completion. They include all their visual and interview data collected over a single academic year.

An attempt is made to show the tentative and the uncertain and this is often suggested using photoshop tools such as showing greater transparency to suggest some weakness or degrees of vulnerability in a student's making or talk. The use of the transparency tool varied as I dialogued with the student and their course work. At times, the transparency tool was used for purely aesthetic purposes (Kirkpatrick et al 2021). The assemblages can also be seen as 'pedagogical portraits' or even 'student report cards' and are intended to be illustrative of a reflexive critical approach to the arts in education (Burnard, and Hennessy, 2006). The full set of assemblages can be found in Chapter 5.

A lot of what I have termed 'visual bluster' can be seen in art departments throughout Scotland and elsewhere; by this I mean work that has maximum visual impact marginalising the ineffable and the tentative and creating instead a kind of 'visual noise' that is so often devoid of subtlety or nuance (Atkinson, 2002; 2018). This can have a 'blustering' if not saturating impact on the learning environment, where pupils feel they too need to adopt these methods of making otherwise known as a 'house style' for the sake of a 'good mark' from the SQA. Figs. 10 and 11 are examples of this kind of making.

Content redacted due to copyright restrictions. Original figure depicts art work. Original figure can be found in Boylan, E and Lightbown, S (2018) National 5 Art and Design. Glasgow: Hodder Gibson. Please contact the thesis author for further information.

Fig. 10 N5 Image (a) courtesy of Boylan and Lightbown, 2018

Candidate A

Your National 5 expressive and design portfolios are submitted to SQA to be marked. Your work is suspended from racks while it is being marked. The work from your school is hung up in alphabetical order.

HINTS & TIPS

You are allowed to submit up to the equivalent of 3 × A2 sheets for each portfolio. This can be presented in a variety of formats, as appropriate (for example, 4 × A3 plus 1 × A2).

Fig.11 N5 Image (b) courtesy of Boylan and Lightbown, 2018

This approach leaves little or no space for a more personalised, enquiry-based art making, where the 'practical and critical mutually inform the other' (Atkinson and Dash, 2005 : xii). There is also little tolerance for consideration of sketchbooks or other forms of 'thinking out' that might have contributed to the making of the 'final piece'. You can see from Fig.11 what a typical display for the SQA assessment looks like. The restricted paper size to A2 is a notable inclusion and a defining aspect of Scottish school art assessment along with the equally restricted number of cut-out images that are put forward as supporting evidence when it would be far more useful

to be able to access a body of supporting work in the form of the aforementioned sketchbook. It is as if you either 'get it' at a glance or you do not. This thesis suggests that this methodology for the assessment of art in schools is deeply damaging to the integrity of the subject and should be revised to allow room for pupils to demonstrate criticality and deep learning.

STEAM EDUCATION AND DRAWING INTO WRITING INTO DRAWING

It is my contention that if we bring pupils' writing closer to their site of art making, we will go some way towards resolving the low levels of written literacy indicated by SQA statistics on the National 5 Art and Design Question Paper (SQA, 2019; Ingold, 2008, 2011). The '*drawing into writing into drawing*' strategy shown in Fig. 7 is intended to address this issue.

I have always argued throughout my creative practice that autographically (in the art making sense) there is little difference between the act of writing and the act of drawing. This point was made forcibly in Klee's *Pedagogical Sketchbook* (Klee, 1953) and in the work of Tim Ingold who brings an anthropological eye to drawing in *Lines* (2008). This thesis owes a debt to both these texts. Furthermore, by going beyond the standardised binary methods of meaning making we enter a whole new world of learning that is necessarily complex, connected and problem based. Later, in the thesis (Chapter 7) I draw attention to a series of interdisciplinary projects that explore the power of the *STEM* (Science, Technology, Engineering and Maths) to *STEAM* (Science, Technology, Engineering, Arts and Mathematics) discourse for our times. Currently, within Scottish school education there is a disconnection in human understanding and how we learn because of a failure of the state to acknowledge the importance of STEM-STEAM argument and promote it (Efland, 2002). By reframing the dialog in schools around the arts and sciences as promised by the *Curriculum for Excellence* reforms you avoid 'silo thinking' and allow a more purposeful interdisciplinary learning to occur (OECD, 2021). This change in thinking would also help reposition the subject of art away from its present and often misguided focus of success being measured in terms of how many applicants they can get into art school. We would also provide a learning environment where initiatives like the *drawing into writing into drawing* initiative become part of the mainstream.

Fig. 12 Drawing into writing into drawing – A Scottish Borders Council Secondary art teachers' in-service (Hawick High School), Circa 2010.

Drawing into writing into drawing is a drawing initiative by myself (McAuliffe, 2010) to embrace literacy using drawing. I had taken for granted the wealth of visual methods embedded in my own fine art education and these have been hitherto undervalued as a skillset. Conducting these workshops throughout schools in Scotland has shown the value that is now placed on visualisation and therefore that skillset. In Fig. 12 art teachers participating in the workshop are responding to a piece of creative writing produced by a junior school student in the English Department of a North Ayrshire secondary school. Metaphors are identified in the writing and visual methods are worked up and applied; soon a visualisation emerges (Hattie, 2012). The purpose of

the exercise was to demonstrate that *drawing into writing into drawing* is a valid strategy that brings the two forms of meaning making closer together. The result is then taken back to class to help the student further improve their writing. This strategy of filtration through drawing can be applied to any form of writing, not just narrative (Riessman, 2008; Kirkpatrick et al 2021).

In seeking to resolve this systemic deficit between words and images where words reign supreme, we risk being entrapped by the hegemony of text-based approaches in teaching and learning. The assemblages presented in this thesis are intended to embody and diffuse through illustration and performativity (Spry, 2001) these long-established divisions and tensions in human understanding (Kress 1997) and to acknowledge that words and images can complement each other. Further examples of this complementarity are the evaluation and academic reading activity presented in Chapter 6.

I have suggested above that we should adopt a tolerance for unknowing where the ineffable and the tentative can flourish and be a valued part of art learning (Baldacchino, 2019). This has implications for assessment where subtlety and suggestion should, arguably, be as measurable as the accuracy and quality of media handling of the standard 'still-life' or 'landscape painting'- the options that continue to dominate state school art in Scotland. The *Advanced Higher* qualification, to whose rewrite I was actively involved a few years ago, has partially secured this meaningful approach to assessment. But unfortunately, due to budgetary restrictions, no other National Qualification in art has since been revised to any great extent and it is unknown when this revision exercise will resume.

With the *Advanced Higher* (AH) qualification pupils are no longer expected to produce tight observational drawings, as illustrated earlier (Fig.11), in fact, the opposite is encouraged. AH pupils are expected to engage in the world of possibilities and reject that learned method of accurately depicting observed form in favour of a more experimental approach using methods more akin to the basic design movement (Yeomans, 1987). But, as suggested earlier, it will take some time before this level of rewrite is cascaded throughout all the National Qualifications (McAuliffe, 2018).

In addition to highlighting the possibilities offered by the synergy of words and images, and the need for the assessment of art in Scottish secondary schools to acknowledge these possibilities, this doctoral project uncovers some of the issues that have prevented the subject thus far from acquiring a more central and critical place in mainstream educational provision. Prior to conducting this study, I was deeply concerned as a teacher educator about the dominance of what appeared to be a highly regulated and narrow skills-based agenda in Scottish secondary art and design education². This was evidenced through the now disbanded SQA Annual Exhibition of art and design exam work (discontinued a number of years ago) where flair and individuality appeared to be suppressed in favour of more homogenous responses. I have argued previously (McAuliffe, 2013, 2018) that a 'culture of compliance' within Scottish education has significantly hindered pupils from gaining access to deeper levels of learning in art (Atkinson, 2002, 2018; Hickman 2005). Furthermore, this perceived privileging of practical skills over 'ideas based' skills has remained largely unchanged resulting in the rise of an 'uncritical arts practice' (Atkinson and Dash, 2005) which now appears to be widely accepted and annually rewarded by the SQA (McAuliffe, 2013, 2014, 2016). These points will be developed further in following chapters.

² The terms art, art education, and art and design education are used interchangeably throughout this text. In schools the subject is often referred to as art, but we know that the use of that term also includes the subject of design. The intention here is that regardless of which term is used it is considered inclusive of both art and design.

CHAPTER 3

THE RESEARCH Design and Story

This chapter expands on the broader design of the research proposed and undertaken including reflections on narrative, visual inquiry, performance of data, case study assemblage and ethics. Later some reflection is offered in key processes of 'troubling the data', visualisation and my related analysis itself is returned to in some depth in Chapters 4 and 5.

Looking back over one of the key DProf pre-module courses on methodology (see appendix 1) *Visual Inquiry*, I needed to adopt a theoretical framework that drew on a range of theories from education (Dewey, 2009; Bruner, 1996), aesthetics (Bachelard, 1994; Wittgenstein, 2015) to the wider field of philosophy. The depth of attentiveness given to the *making of art* as presented in the assessed paper that accompanied this module (see Fig.13 on page 29) was I would argue an example of visual inquiry at its most visceral, yet that attentiveness did not translate into any meaningful written narrative that could ultimately be 'put on display' (Mitchell, 2002:166) to generate this new curricular meaning making that I was seeking (Springgay, Irwin, 2005). I was anxious at the time that I could not shift beyond the binary of writing and/or art making and arrive at some other coherent plateau (Speedy, 2015). The plateau that I would later settle for had not yet emerged as the formation of the 'assemblage' was still being 'worked through'. In the *Visual Inquiry* assignment, consideration has been given, though not 'uncritically' to 'a/r/tography' as one possible 'way-out' (Springgay, Irwin, 2005: 904). 'A/r/tography' can provide the necessary 'attentiveness to what is seen and known and to what lies beneath the surface' of art making. And in the process of conducting this professional doctorate study I have taken full ownership of the research methodology I developed that has been born out of the praxis of art making, the *assemblage*.

We see from Fig. 13 how with the aid of an additional camera (top right) a further layering - a further thickening of the visual inquiry is made available. This level of access to detail helps enrich the narrative thereby helping to cohere it. This composition on page 29 also illustrates that there is no single point of view and that all views are 'perspectival' each with their own narrative (Riessman 2008).

Fig. 13 Stills from a video performance: *I'm going to do 'again' what I normally do*. Art Studio 1, Ayr Campus, (2016) and bottom right *I'm going to do what I normally do*, EVA International Biennial of Contemporary Art, 1999 (McAuliffe, 1999)

Having been 'schooled' in the academy on research design and its methods across a number of institutions in both art and education; I decided in the end not to be wholly guided by those learnt experiences but to instead allow those spaces I had worked in over many years such art-rooms and studio spaces to play a larger role in my thinking (Thomson and Hall, 2021; Bachelard, 1994). I thought these 'aesthetic/poetic spaces' might partially hold the secret to good art and design thinking and making and getting student teachers for example to write in those kinds of places over the recent years has helped alleviate their anxiety and mine too, around academic writing for example (Murray, 2014). This entire research project has been guided by a desire to find methods that are of art *itself* and will help 'story' this research (Hickman, 2008). The assemblage *is* the embodiment of all those methods.

The lure of a clean art-room table can determine all sorts of creative epistemologies, especially if it is a table of such generous proportions as those of the research school (Fig. 14). These tables have been scrubbed of any trace of prior activity but are still full of creative promise. With messy and potentially harmful materials out of the way, an empty table can trigger an opportunity for critical reflection thus potentially resulting in a pedagogical event (Atkinson, 2018). Encountering the work of Atkinson in the late 1990's and especially his text *Art in Education: Identity and Practice* (2002) along with his subsequent tenure as editor of the *International Journal of Art and Design* signalled a shift to a more theory-centred art scholarship from what was then in the early part of the century a rather theory-lite practice-based narrative of the teacher (Steers, 2003). I lost myself in *his* thinking and in the difficulty, it presented to me the reader, as this was not easy reading. It presumed you had done a lot of reading in advance. This level of expectation and difficulty I have come to expect and I am always concerned if I don't encounter it at some level with the students I now work with. It's as if there must difficulty if it's worth knowing. A point advanced by the OECD in their recent review of Curriculum for Excellence (OECD, 2021).

Atkinson had been an art teacher for over a decade, and you knew that his observations were genuine and based on direct experience of the classroom. Atkinson helped the shift in thinking to occur away from 'practice-based' narrative to

a more ideas-based profession which required theoretical thinking to sustain. The Artist-Teacher Scheme had emerged around then as a way of supporting the subject in schools as there seemed to be a growing need for master's provision in education (Galloway, Stanley, and Strand, 2006) We now know that this aspiration was short-lived and soon the scheme ended with the end of the then Labour government in Westminster.

Fig. 14 The research school art-room

The above tables tell their own narrative, they tell us how the subject is valued within the school and show that care and consideration for the subject is clearly present (Noddings, 1984). Thomson and Hall (2021) assert firmly this art-room dimension in a recent paper on 'art room atmosphere'. The pupils in this research also cited the atmosphere of the art-room as a key factor in them deciding to study the subject beyond the statutory two years (S1 and S2).

Following years of conducting classroom observations (Geertz, 2017; Heath, 1985) of beginning art teachers in my role as a teacher educator I recently experienced, through this research, a year's deep observation of 14 pupils within a secondary school art department. To witness, and to notice, to pause, and to stare (Mishler, 1999, Speedy, 2015, Ingold 2011) at the familiar in the context of pedagogy and to try and see it as strange, as unknown (Ranciere, 1991) in order to see it afresh and to own it pedagogically is in essence what this research project has been about.

Art's ineffability in the classroom is where this inquiry began but it is the articulation of *that* phenomenon that has proved so very difficult to advance (Clarke, 2007). Despite having *paused* and *stared at* the making process a 'thousand times' over the course of this study there are still no clear routes to understating this process, this phenomenon.

According to Shields and Irwin (2019, 246) we know that '...artistic inquiry can generate insights into teaching practices' and that '...it is [often] the intention of the art-making to provoke, generate, disrupt and complicate' It is no surprise therefore that given my skill set as painter I chose a fine arts-based method to carry out this research.

The construction of the assemblages presented in Chapter 5 was reliant on not just a fine arts methodology but on a wide range of other associated methodologies, such as narrative. This research concurs with Shields and Irwin (2019) who firmly placed arts-based methods to the fore in their research into art learning. They conceptualise arts-based research as follows:

First, arts-based research is experiential in order to examine the personal, subjective and lived experiences of the participants. Second, it emphasizes emergences, incompleteness, non-linearity, multiple meanings and not knowing. And third it provokes, disrupts and resists traditional ways of doing research in order to examine alternative perspectives (Shields and Irwin, 2019: 247)

The methodological issues at the centre of this project have necessarily invoked a wide-ranging methodological response which includes narrative inquiry (Reissman, 2008); Clandinin and Connelly (2000); Mishler (1999) a/r/tography (Irwin and Springgay, 2008) and autoethnography (Speedy, 2015; Spry, 2001). Drawing upon a number of relatively new methodological tools has enabled this 'seeing' to be

captured and articulated. It was as if, in order to make and give meaning to the data (assemblages), they needed to be organized in a narrative form (Mishler 1999).

To gain a deep pedagogical insight one is compelled to 'hang-out' (Heath, 1985) around the making process in the hope that through immersion one becomes more articulate and insightful about the elusive process of art making. For this to happen, the research had to be located in a supportive environment that was sensitive to the research topic and where one could carefully generate a meaningful dialogue around the art curriculum and pedagogy. The school in which I conducted my inquiry offered this opportunity.

Performing the data

Earlier in the research I encountered the autoethnographic poetry of Tami Spry (2001) where she demonstrates 'possibility' through performativity. Performing poetry and other forms of writing (see appendix 7) on the page as well as the physical space is an integral part of autoethnography (Adams et al, 2015). Becoming aware of autoethnography and how useful it could be to this project was liberating. This led me to consider the performative nature of my own visual research (Adams et al 2015; Bal, 2003). The assemblages are in my view performative. They are doing the showing and telling of the research. Like artwork, it is all there in front of you and 'you don't need to turn any pages' (Hickman, 2008: 53).

Shields and Irwin (2019) argue for:

art-making [not] as a mode representation, but also a mode of narrative inquiry that evokes self-understanding and attempts to express experience (Shields and Irwin 2019: 247)

Like mine, their methods, qualities and outcomes are drawn from art-making practices. In my own art-making I have always wanted to gain a pedagogical understanding and, if possible, narrativise (Mishler, 1999) meaning making and make visible the arts educative dimension (Read, 1958). The methods described thus far were found to be the most suited in capturing the complexity of my field of inquiry.

The narrative dimension (Mishler, 1999) to this study necessitated a 'deep hanging

out' (Geertz, 2017) around pupils and their teachers for a one school year. The fact is that this research was made possible because of teachers and their trust in my motives. They, it appeared, enjoyed the collegiate presence of a researcher in their department for over a year and I was at all times open with them regarding the research progress. This involved being in and around pupils as they attended classes and being allowed to just soak up all that was happening in their learning environment. It could be argued that I was behaving more like an anthropologist (Heath, 1985) than an educational researcher. This behaviour extended to the staff room as I sought to become a full member of staff. I was embedded within the school with high levels of trust granted to me.

Narrative inquiry (Mishler, 1999) was most useful in providing an approach to interviewing that got pupils talking and me listening. I realised early on that the interview could not be a 'first hand' on the practice, and that deep observation was needed as the activity of the interview as a research method would only inform part of the story that I was wishing to tell.

Case study method

I used case study method (Punch, 2005; Crotty, 1998; Clough and Nutbrown, 2012) to observe practice, which in turn helped absorb me into the 'field of inquiry' (Mair, 1989; Heath, 1985), and enabled me to show and tell stories of learning in arts-practice in a secondary school. Each participant represents a case study, and each case is represented by an assemblage (see Chapter 5). Extended periods of 'deep hanging out' in the anthropological sense (Geertz, 1973/2017) around participants' arts-practice in the art-room enabled me to develop an insight into each participant's ways of meaning making and helped me to translate these observations into some form of transcription (Glesne, 1997; Ochs 1979), some form of narrative, and eventually an assemblage.

The transcriptions were used along with the visualisations to form what is now the assemblages - a montage of images and text (Kirkpatrick et al, 2021). An arts-based approach was taken to the process of transcribing the recorded 'learner conversations'. Photoshop was used to combine seamlessly image and text, as the

application aided greatly the understanding I was trying to achieve and created an ideal dialogic platform between the researcher and the researched.

Writing observations of arts-practice and learning in classrooms and furthermore 'writing for inquiry' as expressed by Richardson and St Pierre (2005) has afforded me in the past an 'authorising comfort' around writing (and drawing) enabling me to take risks on how these non-linear forms of meaning making can be presented (Deleuze and Guattari, 1987). Such writings (see Appendix 6) do not conform to standard report writing methods but instead take on a more narrative poetic form (Mair, 1989). It is this form which afforded me the 'authorising comfort' mentioned above.

The learner conversations in this research took the form of semi-structured interviews (Mishler: 2004). These were conducted with each of the participants on a regular basis in the presence and over the course of their personal art and design projects. These interviews or rather learner conversations were written up as close to the time of happening and the writing was intended to function, as earlier mentioned, as a form of inquiry (Mair, 1989) as thick description (Geertz, 1973) was brought to bear on the process.

Ethical Considerations

The protection of the identity of the participants and school involved was paramount. The research stories told by the participants involved have been anonymised through fictionalising their identities. Cognisance and care has been taken of what Pat Sikes (2010: 11) notes as the 'ethical burden' of 're-presenting lives' in educational research.

In line with the BERA (BERA 2018), and UWS's ethics guidelines (2020), participation in the study was always subject to voluntary informed consent (see appendix 4). In order to enable the potential participants to give voluntary informed consent, the purpose of the study and the nature of the participation in it was explained in a participant information sheet (see appendix 6), which was given to all participants. The participants were assured that their identity and that of their school would remain confidential and no details that could lead to their identification would

appear in any reports arising from the study, including the assemblages. In addition, potential participants were informed that they could withdraw from the study at any point. In terms of access to the participants, an art teacher known to me agreed to host the research study in the school in which they worked. Formal permission for this was sought and obtained from the Director of Education for the council where the school is located, and from the Headteacher of the school (see appendix 4)

Learner conversations with pupils from across the age phases of secondary art is an attempt to curate and make visible all that I was inquiring into; that is to say, what learning in and through art looks and sounds like when articulated through the lens of narrative and visual methods (Reissman, 2008; Clandinin and Connelly, 2000; Rose, 2016; Kirkpatrick et al, 2021). It is through the use of these methods that the research story is made to cohere.

Both narrative and visual methods are distinct and separate ways of describing and noticing *in* the world. Through their use here in this study I assert that a fuller range of art learning can be captured and articulated so that pupils come to know, understand and articulate their own learning in the art and design classroom. These narratives, as captured by the 'assemblages', serve as a 'show and tell' of cognitive processes in art (Heaton, 2021) that are essentially rhizomatic: non-linear, fragmented and broken (Deleuze and Guattari, 1987/2013). It is through 'seeing' and 'hearing' these articulations and inarticulations that we begin to recognize and acknowledge the issue of how we get our pupils talking about *their* art learning.

The assemblages carry these narrative accounts and make visible the form that art and art learning takes in the 'grown up world' of education (Biesta, 2017). With the exception of the research school, this seemingly wayfaring way of seeing (Ingold, 2008; Deleuze and Guattari, 1987/2013) and learning is rarely if ever articulated or rewarded by state school examinations in Scotland. However, it is these, sometimes reluctant and vulnerable, visual 'articulations' where pupils can often appear incoherent and even mute in terms of learning that give visual form to pupils' talk and provide us with the possibility of uncovering these fragmented and disrupted lines of inquiry.

We must ask, what does cognition look, and sound like in art and how can we know what is learnt? (Heaton, 2021). How do we improve its articulation for the benefit of the individual and wider community of pupils within and beyond art? These are the kinds of questions we need to ask and answer as art educators. Much needs to be realised such as what learning is seen and unseen, heard and unheard in the classroom, and how do we access, capture and make visible the un-documented learning?

This inquiry need not be seen as abstract or fixed as it exists materially and remains 'active' in terms of data (Pink et al. 2018), that is to say there is a certain fluidity to the data. The assemblages are an attempt to give material form and therefore visibility to this rich cycle of events within learning - we must therefore try to 'see' the assemblages as data, data that can inform and give form to policy and practice in relation to how learners come to know, understand and articulate their learning in art. In line with Shields and Irwin (2019: 245), I

'...resist tendencies to fit arts-based research into social science research and instead propose that arts-based research has its own methods, qualities and outcomes that are drawn from artmaking practices'.

The assemblages created in the course of this research demonstrate that '...the process of meaning-making and being are inextricably connected to an awareness and understanding of art' (Springgay 2005: 63).

The interview Schedule

The following are the nine questions (1.1-1.9) that guided the interviews, however, not all of these were answered by the participants.

1.0 Can you describe what you are doing right now?

1.1 Can you talk me through your process of your art-making? (How have you made this?)

1.2 What was the most difficult aspect of your making?

1.3 What was the least difficult aspect?

1.4 What do you hope to learn by making this? (What is the range of knowledge and skills in arts-practice?)

1.5 What knowledge and skills do you hope to achieve?

1.6 What knowledge and skills are valued by you?

1.7 What knowledge and skills are valued by the school?

1.8 Do you have the subject-specific language to enable you to verbally articulate your learning?

1.9 Do learners need to be able to describe their learning (in verbal and written modes) and if so what are the benefits?

The follow-up four questions (2.0- 2.2) (see page 47) were asked after a period of consideration and discussion with the pupils once the assemblages had been created and shared. The verbatim answers to the interviews are available in Appendix 3 with a select number of pithy statements appearing in the assemblages in Chapter 5.

Troubling the Data: the transcription process

As I listened several times over to the interview recordings and observed pupils' meaning makings for long durations, their hesitations and their ums and ahs (Ochs, 1979; Mishler, 1996; Kirkpatrick et al, 2021) became significant in the transcription process. It took some time before I could make sense of these utterances; the participating pupils' self-doubts are acknowledged in the transcripts by the gaps/spaces/silences in the verbal continuum. These speech acts (Austin, 1976;

Searle, 2008) are reflected too: a close examination of any assemblage will testify vis-à-vis their visual composition of the assemblage.

No formally established system of coding the text was adopted. The decision to represent text in its present form by embedding it within the assemblage derived principally from my reading in a number of areas, such as the field of autoethnography (Kirkpatrick et al, 2021) and especially in the later work by Jane Speedy (2015) in *Staring at the Park*. This along with the methodological advancements of Springgay and Irwin (2005) in *a/r/t/ography* - a popular and influential methodology defined by their use of arts-based research to mean art making / research / theory. The emergence of *a/r/t/ography* within the field of research over the last two decades or so made space for art educators like myself to engage in research. It also encouraged us to bring our creativity into the centre of our research thus allowing and indeed legitimising my own efforts with the emergence of the 'assemblage'. And had *a/r/t/ography* not been so well established by Springgay and Irwin (2005) along with the creative and critical leadership of Hernandez-Hernandez, (2019) I doubt the 'assemblage' would ever have emerged in its present form. Sometimes we just need to take the time to hang out around certain ideas and see if they work.

Eventually, it was settled on what method of visuality to apply to the assemblages. The hand-drawn or autographic drawing approach to visualisation was deemed too invested and too precious. Prior to completing the assemblages, I engaged in a week-long artist-in-residency at the University of Lapland where I had been invited to participate in the 'Relate North 2017' exhibition and conference. Focusing on the conference theme of 'the North' I used the residency as a 'test bed' to explore and trial a single set of data from one of my research participants (Figs 15-17). This participant talked a lot about being up 'North' as they spent most of their holidays in the highlands of Scotland (frequently referred to as 'up North' here in Scotland). I used this participant's data to try to enter into a dialogue around what a Northern pedagogy might look like. This was the subject of my conference paper which I would deliver later that week.

I saw for example how the pedagogy of Room 13 flourished helped by being away from 'the centre' of attention in a rural school in the Scottish Highlands (Gibb, 2012;

Adams and Owen, 2015). This was also my time to demonstrate how I might use drawing to 'draw out' and make visible my research data (Rose, 2016).

The decision to move the visualisation process to digital was taken following the residency and I soon adopted *Photoshop* as the preferred tool. The paper-based hand drawn approach, whilst deeply visceral (Ingold, 2008) became too precious and very personal, that is to say, these were becoming artworks, my artworks, my drawings. I needed to take some distance. I felt I had to find a more neutral form - a more neutral voice. Also given the practicalities of the research and the need to adjust the transcription for accuracy of representation, *Photoshop* could do this with ease and with a 'neutral' hand. We know that autographic drawing is powerful and responsive (ibid) but for this project it was deemed too powerful, too invested. The *Photoshop* 'layering' and 'cutting' tools were eventually applied to give strength and clarity as well as show weakness and vulnerability in the pupils' voice (Ochs, 1979).

Fig. 15 (Top) View from outside the Relate North Residency Studio, University of Lapland, November 2017. Fig. 15 (Bottom) Monitor with a close-up view of inside the Studio

Fig. 16 Work in Progress (No.1) from Relate North Residency, University of Lapland, November 2017

Fig. 17 Work in Progress (No.2) from Relate North Residency, University of Lapland, November 2017

Using *Photoshop* as the preferred method in which to blend, combine and cut away data, I brought together the interview transcripts, the interview analysis and key themes, the artwork the student was working on over the period of this study, and, where needed, photographs of their learning environment.

Vulnerability was often on display in a student's voice but rarely is it displayed in their final course work. It is as if to show weakness or vulnerability in their final art projects is to demonstrate poor or weak art learning, and how would such a narrative ever be permitted to prevail? Everything is arguably tentative for the duration of the learning. The multi layered soundscape of an open-plan classroom (where the research was conducted) leads to a 'multi-pedagogised space' (Atkinson, 2002) where one pedagogy is fighting with another for attention. It is a crowded environment and subtlety is often suppressed and even overlooked by the noise —quite literally the noise in this instance that comes with the open-plan environment (see Figs 18,19,20), an environment that is replicated at the assessment stage too where subtlety often loses out in cavernous spaces of the SQA assessment hall for art and design.

Fig. 18 The Open Plan Art Rooms, (View A)

Fig. 19 The Open Plan Art Rooms, (View B)

Fig. 20 The Open Plan Art Rooms, plus storage and display areas (View C)

Reflecting back on the literature that I have engaged with during the writing up of this research, Denis Atkinson contribution vis-à-vis his use of the term a 'multi

pedagogised space' is to me one of the most embodied of concepts (Atkinson, 2002). He gets inside the concept and appears to articulate it from the *inside*. This notion was viscerally felt when present in the classrooms of the research school.

One finding that is dominant from this research is that the participating pupils did not seem verbally equipped to talk about their work with flow and coherence. In fact, there was rarely flow, just a stagger of words which the pupils hoped would get them over the line (see interview transcripts in Appendix 3). Biesta would refer to this as the pupils' own struggle to enter the 'grown up world' of articulation (Biesta 2015). To write out is to draw out (Ingold 2008) and it was hoped that through invoking narrative and visual methods the two forms would cohere to give voice. Writing out in the sense of transcribing pupils' spoken words is akin to drawing out bit by bit someone's thinking. It is not composed and refined through drafting and redrafting but remains rather raw, broken, and inarticulate (Deleuze and Guattari, 1987/2013).

Troubling the data: a process for analysis

Data in this study resists being reduced to any one form and is represented here as an embodied set of images and texts per case study (assemblage). This signified a return to my fine art practice, as referred to earlier, where I could begin to embody and make visible a disparate set data and tell the research story by showing (Denzin and Lincoln, 2018).

Never before had I considered that I was a maker of data. Never before, that is to say before starting this Professional Doctorate, did I consider image making on a par with data generation in the social sciences (Pink, 2013). I now fully appreciate why artists make art and indeed need art to show and tell their research stories. Or as Hofsess, Riddett, and Siegesmund (73: 2019) put it '[w]e have to take things and find visibilities in them'.

Method of analysis

I set out to use a method of analysis that would not be alienating to the teachers and pupils with whom I worked but instead would prove beneficial to both constituents in advancing their use of visual methods for purposes of reflexivity in the classroom (Mishler, 1999; Baptista, 2018). It was important that the tool of analysis would be of

the field of 'art' hence the assemblage, and that the pupils could relate to the rationale provided for its use. In the end, the data set on each student has served as a kind of 'pedagogical portrait' of the student – a record of an attempt to capture the essence of what they had achieved – a sort of visual report card on their achievement. My engagement with the pupils drew to a close once the pupils had the opportunity to absorb the content of their assemblage and engaged in a dialogue around the findings

The use of arts-based methods allowed for the capture of 'messy' data that is not easily represented or accounted for in social sciences research such as drawings, photographs, paintings, and 3D forms (see Appendix 6). Narrative arts-based research opens up areas of learning that have been previously hidden and silent, through making visible *all* components of the learning *vis-à-vis* visualization/ assemblage process (see Appendix 6 and 7)

It is important to recognize how the artistic process is reflected in the construction of this thesis so that the thesis 'performs the artmaking rather than just represent it' (Shields and Irwin 2019: 252). The process of turning subjects (the pupils' learning) into objects (Mishler 1999:151) to be analysed using visual methods provides a comprehensive and coherent picture of what was being researched. It attempted to make visible the reality of this research. Turning 'subjects into objects' raises a number of ethical concerns such as the shift from single authorship of the pupils' own art works and interviews to joint authorship where the researcher has collaged the various forms of data to create a single image in the form of an 'assemblage'. This is where the pupils can see their work and read their words and 'hear their own voices' over the course of their study.

Mishler tells us that '[t]elling stories is one of the significant ways individuals construct and express meaning' (1996: 67) and we show how stories are developed to a point where they resonate. The assemblages resonated with the participants and this is evidenced through the feedback received from the pupils when presented with their assemblage just before 'lockdown'³ on my final day at the research school

³ The term 'lockdown' should be understood within the context of the international coronavirus pandemic.

in March 2020. On this day I sought to validate the assemblage as a research methodological device and I did so by asking the pupils the following three questions.

- How do you think the visualisation has captured your understanding of your learning?
- How do you think the visualisation has captured our conversation?
- Is there a place for concept visualisation in art learning?

Not all pupils who participated in the research were present but many were (n.6) and their responses feature in the next Chapter – composing a visual narrative.

CHAPTER 4

COMPOSING A VISUAL NARRATIVE (what the case study assemblages tell us)

Fig. 21 A view from the office window, University of the West of Scotland Ayr Campus

Using visual methods to construct the narrative

Inquiry interrogates, inquiry opens up previously concealed spaces, in previously unknowable zones (Pink, 2013; Punch, 2005; Sullivan, 2010). The above image is deeply significant to this research so much so that it features in all of the assemblages as a kind of ‘watermark’ or ‘seal of approval’ consistent with an artist’s signature. This photographic ‘thumbnail’ features mainly towards the lower half of each assemblage. Essentially, it is a ‘visual device’ that serves as a helpful reminder to me as the researcher and maker of these assemblages of what visual complexity looks and feels like (Rose, 2016). This single photographic image signifies a seminal moment of reflection, which in this case is made up of a multi-layered set of screens, planes and surfaces reflected on my office window. All of the assemblages in

Chapter 4 should be read to convey the complexity of meaning making that went on in the art-rooms of the research school. Fig. 21 should be read to mean the following:

Reflections upon deep reflections on the narrow windowpane before me in my place of work is there to be troubled and theorized – it is Velazquez’s ‘Las Meninas’ writ large where everyone is watching everyone, not unlike the setting in your average art-room. What is real and what is not is impossible to say. This is a perfect arena in which to problematise normative methods of doing and saying. The image itself manifests as a site of reflection and thus a site of research and is a useful reminder that reading pupils’ artwork is multifaceted and should be approached with great care and attention (Rose, 2016; Noddings, 1984). The image before me is of planes and constructs that go towards ‘making sense’ of the ordinary.

In working towards this thesis, I engaged in a course of studies in the areas of visual methods and autoethnography at the University of Bristol. I found these courses helpful as I pursued a visual narrative investigation into the complex question of how learners come to know, understand and articulate their own learning (Glesne, 1997; Kress and Van Leeuwen, 2001).

Autoethnography and messy texts

Autoethnography has a rich history of subverting traditional forms of writing, through ‘messy texts’ (Denzin, 1997) and other forms of meaning making emanating from ‘studio thinking’ (Hetland, et al 2013) - a form of thinking and making that is unique to the studio setting. This aspect will be further developed in Chapter 6 of the thesis.

In conducting this research I drew on the work of Jane Speedy (Speedy, 2015), Tami Spry (In Kirkpatrick, et al 2021), Tim Rollins and KOS (Rollins, 2012) (see Appendix 7) along with a lot of graduate work that has emerged recently out of the University of British Columbia (Gillard in Sinner, Irwin and Jokela, 2018) and has been promoted in seminal texts such as *Provoking the Field* (2019) by Sinner, Irwin and Adams. Here art educational research appears to be right at the confluence of art, writing and performance and has provided the field with much hope and scope for

change even at school level. Suggestions will be made later as to how this can be taken further.

Fig. 22 Arranging the Assemblages in the Studio, Ayr Campus

Fig. 23 Completed display of the Assemblages, Ayr Campus

The Pupil Voice made visible from Secondary 1-6

I begin with the three Secondary one pupils, known in Scottish Education as S1 (11-12 years old) (Maura, Lewis and Chen) and isolate their salient responses to two questions in particular in this opening section – a fuller transcript is available in Appendix 2. I draw on the seminal text on transcription by Ochs (1979) to support this move. Ochs (1979: 44) tells us that ‘a more useful transcript is a more selective one’ and this research maintains that view and has demonstrated this in the assemblages. This has been done by selecting pithy statements from the participants. Following on from S1, the narrative then works through to the end stage of secondary schooling in Scotland known as Secondary 6 (S6).

Maura, a 1st year student was asked to respond to question 1.8

Do you have the subject-specific language to enable you to verbally articulate your learning? She responded

I don't have the words/language to describe (sic)

Chen, another 1st year was asked the following:

1.9 Do learners need to be able to describe their learning (in verbal and written modes) and if so, what are the benefits?

I don't know how to describe it!

I think you need to be able to describe your learning

You need to know why you are doing it.

If you know how to speak about it, it means you really do know what you are doing!

In the first year of secondary education in Scotland, pupils normally study art and design for, on average, three fifty-minute periods a week (Scottish Government); though in some schools in recent years this has been reduced to two and replaced with an additional period of physical education⁴. The main concern of the class teachers at this level is with the material and technical nature of the subject therefore learning how to draw and handle art materials becomes essential.

⁴ Over the last ten years or so there has been a crisis in the Health and Wellbeing of certain demographics in Scotland resulting in a rise in the obesity levels of pupils. To try to address this issue the Scottish Government decided in some schools to remove a period of art a week and replace it with PE.

The pupils at S1 are essentially working at a level below S1 (McAuliffe, 2013; 2014; 2018) and need to be taught very basic skills in drawing and meaning making. However, an unambiguous finding from this cohort in response to the nine questions in general and in relation 1.8 and 1.9 specifically was that they identified a deficit in their learning in the use of spoken and written language within art and design (Clarke, 2007). This finding is aligned with a teacher led concern with 'learner articulation', which is now overwhelmingly substantiated by the SQA exam data. As noted in Chapter 1, the 2019 SQA results for the National 5 art and design question paper uncovered that the average grade-mark nationally for the written paper was a fail and this has been the case ever since these new qualifications began. Could it be that this paper is not fit for purpose and this assessment needs to be reformulated into something more fitting? Or should schools be teaching more robustly the critical and contextual questions that accompany the subject? This failure serves to undermine art learning in a number of ways, most notably pupils are unable to describe what they have learnt following an art lesson.

Gert Biesta, (2017) in *Letting Art Teach, Art Education 'after' Joseph Beuys* suggests that it is now not enough to let art to speak for itself because we live in an age of accountability where pupils need to be able demonstrate that they have met certain success criteria. Statements like *'I don't have the words to describe'* (Maura S1) were frequently stated not just in first year but throughout all year groups and this points towards a certain learner vulnerability around spoken and written language that has not been sufficiently acknowledged by the state. It is a concern that this study sheds some light on.

In the Second-Year group of this S1-S6 cohort, there is again further evidence of a desire to articulate to others one's art learning in verbal and written modes and this capacity to communicate was important to the pupils. Anxieties remain in relation to the language deficit with statements like *'a lot of things are hard to describe'* and *'pupils need to be able to describe their learning'* (Jason a 2nd year student). This issue further points to another overarching issue in Scottish education - the aversion to difficult learning, which was referred to by the Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) in their recent review of *Curriculum for Excellence* (OECD, 2021).

A greater sense of agency emerged within the Year Three group (S3) with pupils from arguably opposite ends of the learning spectrum being interviewed. Logan, at the upper-end was confident when interviewed but displayed just a little reticence when asked if he had acquired the necessary language capacity to help describe his learning. He said *'I think I have the language to describe [my learning]'*. He referred to the subject of English in his response stating he *wished to be creative and imaginative like in (sic) English*. This response prompted me to enquire into whether any alliances across subject disciplines had been possible. It should not be controversial to suggest that teaming up with another subject discipline such as English might be usefully called upon to assist in some way; this theme is revisited in Chapter 5 when we look at reframing the dialogue between subjects.

Ava, another S3 student felt unable to articulate her own learning, stating that *'I don't think I can describe what I am doing'* and *'I'm very creative in my mind but not so on paper'*. Ava, talked about *'doing things that are not fully understood by pupils'* and *'showing development through materials'*. She exclaimed that *'landscape is very boring'* but had no difficulty settling on creativity and patience as being the main outcomes of her learning. Returning to the point of *'doing things that are not fully understood'*, I believe Ava was referring to the demands of the National 5 exam, which she was due to undertake.

Secondary Four (S4) sees the pressure of time become visible to pupils. Douglas sums this up cogently when he speaks of time in relation to his National 5 art and design studies, stating that *'this is what time looks like'* when staring at his incomplete N5 coursework. And for the very first time too pupils are having to come to terms with their first external examination. Douglas acknowledges that this leads to a greater understanding of one's own art making when he states: *'you understand your work better when you write about it...and 'to speak is to understand'*. These remarks raise interesting pedagogical questions for the place of writing and indeed reading in informing critical debate in art in schools in Scotland.

Since sitting the N5 Question Paper, Douglas observed that he *'struggled with the language'* as *'it wasn't his own work he was having to critique'*. Throughout his

studies and up until this year, his note taking was '*mainly photographic and verbal*' and concerned *his* own artwork. Having to critique the work of others was another matter entirely for which he felt he was not fully prepared. Pupils do find their own ways of note taking but these methods such as taking photographic notes are not always applicable to SQA question paper.

The pressure to perform at the National 5 exams raised a certain anxiety for Amira (S4). She loved the discipline of painting but was frustrated by the limiting amount of critical and historical engagement she received. Time was against Amira as it was with all the others. Amira was serious about all her studies and cared for learning. To see how she cared for her art making was impressive. She spoke with such elegance and humility that you could feel and see her aesthetic understanding.

Pupils in the fifth year of study select a theme for 'Expressive Studies' and a theme for 'Design Studies' known at school level as 'Expressive' or 'Design'. For the Expressive component objects are often assembled into a still-life' which may or may not have personal meaning to the student; this is also the case for Design. This research is suggesting that not enough time is afforded to the discussion around making these choices. That is to say, aesthetic questions are not afforded enough time, another example where 'studio thinking' (Hetland, et al 2013) could benefit a student. The studio is where pupils get their words, that is through thinking and making.

Objects of study should be 'troubled' over thus avoiding a situation, as Valter (S5) describes, when he had to draw a musical instrument (flute) which he could not play, and did not fully empathise with. Valter was certain that the pupils' *own studio making was critical to aiding their understanding of the question paper.*

He also believed that '*you [would] have a better understanding of your own work where you are able to describe it. 'Paint is slow...' 'I learnt to stray from the image...' 'But I feel like there is a bit of something I'm lacking in when talking about the art work.'*

Chrissie (S5) was an anxious learner and although she could and did complete her Higher Art, she had all sorts of anxieties including how her work was going to be

marked by the SQA – the lack of transparency around ‘the marking’ raises questions for all art teachers in Scotland. She also admitted to having very little art specific language, stating she had *‘a bit of language but I don’t know why (sic). We don’t really get taught that...’* Chrissie reiterated what others had said across the year groups that *‘if you are able to describe your learning you are able to understand it’(sic)*.

A pedagogical shift occurs in art departments when pupils move into Advanced Higher (S6) as the ‘guy ropes’ are removed and pupils begin to realise that in order to progress to the next level they need to unlearn much of what they have previously been taught (Baldacchino, 2017). This radical shift in pedagogical thinking, which is more akin to ‘studio thinking’ (Hetland, et al 2013), is rarely fully articulated to pupils, as expectations are raised that pupils will now need to reject the previously formulaic approaches to art making and learning and reach instead for more creative and experimental methods. Other than explaining through practical demonstration, it appears that pupils are not encouraged to read in and through the conceptual machinations that a shift in thinking of this order might demand. From my observations, it would seem that very little reading is occurring at this phase of learning and this stood out as an obvious barrier to dealing with difficult concepts such as ‘not knowing’. These concepts clearly need to be ‘read-into’ if they are to be fully understood, let alone adopted as a method of making and thinking (Baldacchino, 2017). The near pedagogic certainty that was promoted in their learning up to this stage is now quite quickly replaced with doubt as ‘not knowing’ becomes a central tenet to the learning at this advanced level (Atkinson, 2018; Baldacchino, 2017; McWilliam, 2005; Smith 2016).

Pupils at this senior phase were concerned about the transferability of their learning and how they might articulate their learning in art as their art educational world becomes increasingly more complex. Some suggested that *‘maybe a few lessons on ‘how to talk about your work would be good’*. Along with having to now abandon the certainty of working with the formulaic processes of art making that have ‘served’ pupils for the past five years, many pupils are still unable or struggle to describe and write about what it is they are learning in the simplest of terms. It is not therefore enough to simply develop a tolerance for ‘messiness’ and ‘not knowing’ at this

advanced stage in their learning. The accompanying critical discourse needs also to be developed and this can only happen when deep reading of often difficult texts is encouraged (Biesta, 2017).

In Chapter 5, the reader is invited to consider the 14 assemblages that are the centrepiece of this thesis and to read for themselves what these are asserting. These images speak for themselves as if they were on show in a portrait gallery. Indeed, it is the intention of the researcher to place them in this or a similar context within the next year or so to enable the participants (and their families) to see the fruits of this research.

CHAPTER 5

THE CASE STUDY ASSEMBLAGES (from Secondary 1-6)

Fig. 24 Case Study Assemblage No. 1

Maura

Fig. 25 Case Study Assemblage No. II

Chen

1.0 Can you describe what you are doing right now?
 So we've been doing a portrait. I have been looking in the mirror to see our features. And we've been doing it so it's more exact because a lot of us are drawing it a bit cartoony. So to get it more realistic and to get the exact proportions really of your face.

1.1 Can you talk me through your process of your art-making? (How have you made this?)
 So what I did I halved it to get the middle point. And then I put a line across the paper use your fingers from measurements and just where the knuckle is is one measurement and we did 5 along and 3.5 up that's how we measured the proportions. And we drew circle to get our eyes and then we looked closely at our eyes to see what shape they are.

1.2 What was the most difficult aspect of your making?
 Probably getting in the eyes right because they're quite hard to do right but that just shows where you need to practice.

1.3 What was the least difficult aspect? It's probably just doing the measurements because you just use your fingers and it's easy to fix your mistakes and things like that it's just easier really.

1.4 What do you hope to learn by making this? (What is the range of knowledge and skills in arts-practice?)
 To get the right proportions drawing my face and to improve from my previous portrait. And To take away the skills that I can do this without any help.
 Just as an aside do you think we still need to draw in this way given that we have cameras? Yeah because you know cameras... drawing is a skill we need to do.
 I would like to do.
 Why?
 Knowing that you're doing is really like if I take a picture it's the phone doing all the work. But if I'm drawing it I know in myself I done it the drawing.

1.5 What knowledge and skills do you hope to achieve?
 Some self-confidence in knowing new can do this and that's the main thing for me.

1.6 What knowledge and skills are valued by you?
 1.7 What knowledge and skills are valued by the school?
 I think they are looking for improvement in your drawings just in the whole that you're drawing better improving because that's all they can for really.

1.8 Do you have the subject-specific language to enable you to verbally articulate your learning?
 I think I'm still improving ...but am I still need to learn some vocabulary.
 Have you learnt any new words Not particularly but I think I will for sure.

1.9 Do learners need to be able to describe their learning (in verbal and written modes) and if so what are the benefits?
 I think am just being able talk about your learning means you know what you're doing hundred percent am it's good to be able to talk about what you're learning.

**If you know how to speak about it,
 it means you really do know what you are doing!**

Fig. 26 Case Study Assemblage No. III

Lewis

Fig. 27 Case Study Assemblage No. IV

Jason

Fig. 28 Case Study Assemblage No. V

Jo

Fig.29 Case Study Assemblage No. VI

Jessica

I think I have the language to describe

How to design things better

Fig. 31 Case Study Assemblage No. VIII

Logan

time was the most difficult aspect of the making

You have to think of everthing

1.0 Can you describe what you are doing? Aerial design well this is the side and we were meant to side so I started the front and back so were having to pick a theme and we were making a head piece piece of armour and I thought would be good to reptiles exploring reptiles and layers quite good I thought underwater structures would be good with metallic colours I've done a lot of metallics so of grey silver colour I thought those colours would go really nicely together and look good a piece of armour

Very clear process

Time involved remains the most difficult aspect

1.1 Can you describe what you are doing? Well its just like cutting out designs see for this one just very simple

1.2 What was the most difficult aspect of your making? **Intricacy and precision - a valued skill**

1.3 What was the least difficult aspect? **Attention to detail**

1.4 What do you hope to learn by making this? What is the range of knowledge and skills in arts-practice?

1.5 What knowledge and skills do you hope to achieve?

1.6 What knowledge and skills are valued by you? **You would understand your work better when you write about it**

1.7 What knowledge and skills are valued by the school? **To speak is to understand**

1.8 Do you have the subject-specific language to enable you to verbally describe your work? **looking at things in more depth and with more care**

1.9 Do learners need to be able to describe their learning (in your words) and if so what are the benefits?

Questions follow in the re-presentation of the data in the form of:

2.0 How do you think the visualisation has captured your understanding of your learning?

2.1 How do you think the visualisation has captured your understanding of your learning?

2.2 Is there a place for you in the visualisation?

I struggled with the language because it wasn't my own work it wasn't personal to me

Dedication of time

Fig. 32 Case Study Assemblage No. IX

Douglas

Fig. 33 Case Study Assemblage No. X

Amira

I don't really know what knowledge and skills are valued by me.

I cannot say entirely why we are doing this.

I don't know how it's going to be marked by SQA!

1.0 Can you describe what you are doing right now?

So I'm making a headpiece for design. So kind of based around sleeping beauty so the kind of spirally what's it called the spindle wheel sewing wheel and kind of flowers that go with that. And feathers screws and stuff lots of lots of pink that fits into that but make it look like a headpiece... we've done tracings kind of followed it and copied it. There is meant to be symmetry in then do a structural piece. [are these words? It looks like it.]

Taking your time - time keeping - art and design has taught me this!

So this is just development want to make a big... with the spirals I've got wee beads which I'll add to the headpiece.

So how long is it taking you to do this?

These took two periods which is an hour and 40 minutes.

1.1 Can you talk me through your process of your art-making? (How have you made this?)

So we start off with pictures we've got off the Internet and Pinterest. So I've got pictures of flowers things like that and to draw the out of the full face of and...

The not knowing in terms of marks is a concern

1.2 What was the most difficult aspect of your making?

So trying to make them look as lifelike as possible so things all match up, so I don't want to look all cartoony. So I quite like stuff when it looks realistic

1.3 What was the least difficult aspect?

The colouring in so once you've drawn all out it's quite therapeutic I've not have to think too hard about it. So I just picked for different colours.

1.4 What do you hope to learn by making this? (What is the range of knowledge and skills in arts-practice?)

1.5 What knowledge and skills do you hope to achieve?

Don't quite like to say what this is for... I'd like to look all put together I'd like to show it I'd like to show it I'd like to show the pictures and say where that came from...

1.6 What do you would find this valuable for you?
If you are able to describe your learning you are able to understand it

1.7 What knowledge and skills are valued by the school?

I'm not sure honestly. Timekeeping and being able to do something in the time given. Making it look really nice and not rushing out.

1.8 Do you have the subject-specific language to enable you to verbally articulate your learning? I am not very good is saying what I'm doing not very good at articulating it. I don't know why we doing some things at times.

I know it's self-development and stuff I don't just don't know what the language would be.

1.9 Do

I have a bit of language but I don't know why.

learners need to be able to describe their learning in verbal and written modes and if so what are the benefits? It makes you understand it better if you're able to say. Like in history if your topic you don't know what are you doing it's you will be able to understand it.

Fig. 35 Case Study Assemblage No. XII

Chrissie

1.0 Can you describe what you are doing right now?

Amm well in Advanced Higher art, we're choosing a certain... well I'm doing architecture so I'm choosing buildings and I've kinda went down the realms of New Orleans and those type of buildings and will choose those subject matters and we'll say use charcoal and do different drawings of them and then maybe move on to different pens or aam aaam like other structures of these buildings and archways and stuff like that and aaa creating a big folio basically in these sketchbooks it then gets sent away to prove how we've got to our final boards and stuff.

1.1 Can you talk me through your process of your art-making? (How have you made this?)

It might be useful to see you something

Okay I'll go and get it.

Brilliant excellent

quite big books that we're working with

This will really help us I feel

Amm So we'll go online and we'll maybe go onto pinterrest or something like that and we'll find... see like that is basic New Orleans kinda house to me is what I think of so we'll kinda draw like what I have done with ink there, pencil and pencil again and these are all just mark makings to describe an archway

Amm So it's just kind of like picking an image from online and seeing what we can create out of that one image and then there was like this one, I kind of focused more on this part of the building and I extended some about me bigger versions of it and that was charcoal some of the structures that I've seen here ari and stuff like that this was a printmaking stage to be done as well so we chose laminate take up these little like blades they have big handles and stuff for them so you could kind of carve it out and you put ink over it and press it on different things like polyester

All not polyester

Polystyrene

oh that's the one

Being okay with messiness

And we were like carving into that and doing loads of printmaking

It was just kind of like choosing an image and seeing what we can create from it and zooming in on certain aspects of the image and stuff like that

1.2 What was the most difficult aspect of your making?

I don't think I was consistent

So I think on this page this was one of my best drawings

And then I don't really like these ones I've done that with pen the one that was pencil

So I think with that image pen would be better

If you know what I mean trying to keep your all of your work in a consistent level I think is the hardest part of it

Your mistakes are good in art are always good I guess it is

They're always good to see

You've got to certain images and stuff like that

1.3 What was the least difficult aspect?

Amm I think once I've got once I've got an image that I've printed off and have stuck into my book I think the

easiest part for me is like what I did just now

I think it's just like what I will do first so when I printed that off first basically the same image that's obviously not

drawing in pen I'm from that I was like what else can I draw that I think it's quite easy to go through different

like techniques and stuff going through a full pen and stuff and I find it easy to get a full-page done within half

an hour sometimes

1.4 What do you hope to learn by making this? (What is the range of knowledge and skills in arts practice?)

I think it shows with these sketchbooks that your mistakes aren't the worst thing in life I think that what it shows see look at this

It shows how my sketches in this the worst thing but then my teachers say I know but so I like it because messy making a

mistake is sometimes really good and it's not always a bad thing to make mistakes shows what it's like in life as well

It shows with these sketchbooks that your mistakes aren't the worst thing

1.5 What knowledge and skills do you hope to achieve?

I don't really know with art especially, you don't really know (not in a bad way) you don't really know what you are doing until it's achieved

and I don't know what you are doing until it's achieved, I'm just taking pictures at the moment. And I would say to the teacher what am I doing next and she would say just keep going

and I'm sure it will you know what I know so I think I don't know really... I really don't know.

1.6 What knowledge and skills are valued by you?

I don't really know, when I just think you know what you are doing when you come in to art and I'll figure out this is what

you're going to do today, right that's very good that's what I'm going to do, sometimes I'll do something very quickly

and this page quite messy

That's not a good way to be within art

Just coming into it, you don't really need to know exactly what you're doing

And I think you can just continue on from there

1.7 What knowledge and skills are valued by the school?

Amm I think in the school, I think with National 5 and Higher Art, I think it's all very structured for the first and do this and do this

and I quite like I quite like that you're just there scribbling over a page making art and I think that's what art is it's not very structured that's why

I like how really do within the art department it's very you do you do what you think

I think the school needs to realise this is how art is made

And still do not know What I'm going to do for my final but it's just that way of getting yourself in that mindset do you know that I mean

1.8 Do you have the subject-specific language to enable you to verbally articulate your learning?

I don't really know (what do you mean?) a language that is associated with art. I'm doing maths right now and with maths you're going with the formulas.

In art you are very free and with maths you can't be free

because you are going with the rules of maths

In art you are very free it's okay to have mistakes it's like to be okay with messiness and stuff in English you need to be a very particular with your work very neat and very to the rules

and that's why I like art so much you come in is just like on you go and find things and go and make art

1.9 Do learners need to be able to describe their learning (in verbal and written modes) and if so what are the benefits?

Wait and see how how I could describe art too people

See when I'm talking to my parents about art I feel it is very hard to describe art because no one can get in into your head even teachers

Fig. 37 Case Study Assemblage No. XIV

Catriona

CHAPTER 6

CONCEPT VISUALISATION: WIDER APPLICATIONS

This chapter offers further insight to both my own data collection and analysis but also presents a forum for professional practice reflection in regard of my expression as artist and educator and this research study's broader contribution. I refer to this in more detail in the concluding section of this chapter (see page 82)

The following series of vignettes are concept visualisations with accompanying reflective texts generated by Professional Graduate Diploma in Education (PGDE) art and design teacher education students towards the end of the 2018-19 academic year. This was an arts-based evaluative task designed to increase engagement in the evaluation/assessment process - a task, that if only written, would have been considered tedious and mundane for this set of post-graduate students (Hickman, 2008, Leavy 2019).

Engaging in these visualisation tasks really strengthened the case for the adoption of the assemblage as the format I would select to create these pupil profiles – I had years of experience doing this with student teachers I knew the value of the process.

The following illustrates that it is possible for image and text to coexist (Kress and van Leeuwen, 2001) and indeed complement, each other, thus negating the privilege that is afforded text across education more generally. When asked later about the process, these PGDE students stated that they were 'driven by the image' but that it also 'helped them to write more meaningfully'.

Their initial brief by the PGDE programme leader, was to produce a 1000 word written evaluation at the end of a five-week teaching placement in a secondary school. Given the dominance of text-based pedagogies to which I referred earlier, the assumption has always been that this would be a 'written task', an assumption that is now very misguided and frankly out of date (Kress and van Leeuwen, 2001). However, since I now had acquired the making learning visible skill set (Hattie, 2012)

made possible by this research, I switched their brief from a requirement to *write*, to a requirement to use *visual methods* (Hickman, 2008; Rose, 2015) and since these were art trained individuals they seized the opportunity and got to work. The case of 'the artwork' as a central conduit for the reporting of classroom experience within the context of teacher education has been cogently made here by Hickman (2008) and others such as Eisner (1995) and Barone and Eisner (1997; 2012). Hickman argues that the artwork is all there in front of you and that you don't need to turn any pages (Hickman, 2008). This act of meditating on a single image to deeply read its inherent educational concern provides further evidence of the value of 'staring' (Speedy, 2015) and by extension the assemblages. The pupils concluded the task with a paragraph of reflective writing which explained the usefulness of what they had achieved whilst unpacking the more hidden aspects of the visualisation.

Hickman goes on to list the following benefits of using the visual art form as a vehicle to convey meaning:

- Visual art forms can capture the ineffable, helping us to gain access to the more elusive aspects of the teaching and learning enterprise and reveal phenomena which would be difficult to perceive and understand through words (and numbers) alone.
- They demand our attention, engaging both affective and cognitive faculties.
- They can present the whole reported episode at one time, enabling the viewer to see relationships between the whole and its parts.
- They can provide a rich yet economical, multilayered source of information by using, for example, metaphor, analogy and iconography.
- They can transform the apparent mundanity of day-to-day reality into something more meaningful through altering our perceptions of the ordinary.
- They are widely accessible, through the use of shared visual convention.

(Hickman, 2008:9)

Fig.38 End of Placement Evaluation, 2019 (Student A)

This piece is woven together using strips of the Expressive Arts, Health and Wellbeing, Numeracy and Literacy Experiences and Outcomes as well as the GTCS Standards for Registration

Using weaving as a construction method for this piece is an acknowledgement of my previous studies and career [this student was a textiles graduate who went on to work in the industry before applying to Teacher Education]. However, it is also being used to highlight one of the most successful schemes of work delivered during my school experience when considering both learning and teaching.

The process of weaving the strips also symbolises my developing knowledge, understanding and skills from each teaching placement being brought together to give me a strong starting point for the probationary year ahead.

The addition of colour was a reflection on the need to adapt to the availability of resources at different schools and having to find creative ways to make the most of limited materials.

Fig. 39 End of Placement Evaluation, 2019 (Student B)

Standing on the shoulders of giants... This piece reflects the nurturing and supportive environment of my final placement. The more completed hand represents my colleagues who have vast experience and knowledge of the practice coming together with the hand which is still incomplete representing myself. I chose to leave this hand incomplete as although I feel far better prepared throughout this teaching

year and being supported by some fantastic members of the profession, I still believe I have a lot that I could learn to better inform my practice. I have a lot of enthusiasm and excitement to network with others and develop my skills even further which is represented by the key words in the creases of the hand.

This piece also represented a worry of mine when I first started as a student teacher, I was concerned that I may have to speed up the pace of my art work for exemplar purposes. This is something I have been working on throughout the year and thus I limited the time I could spend on this exemplar which resulted in it still being unfinished but exemplifying more confidence than the start of the year.

The clasped hands symbolise the nurture I have been provided in learning and that of which I wish to provide to learners in my NQT year and career beyond.

Fig. 40 End of Placement Evaluation, 2019 (Student C)

Perhaps somewhat on-the-nose here (sic), but this evaluation is intended to represent a feeling of constant observation during PGDE- this could be from tutors, school mentors, pupils or even the expectation of family and friends. While this has been beneficial in its own way, it has certainly led to a certain degree of paranoia and discomfort on my part. I am looking forward to being allowed to “get on with teaching” to a greater degree in the coming years, though I suspect I may just be trading out these sets of watchful eyes for another!

Fig. 41 End of Placement Evaluation, 2019 (Student D)

This piece is unfinished, in the same way my journey to becoming a successful teacher is. This is part of an exemplar for a first-year portraiture project which in turn, was also used and painted in my final crit. The idea of the piece being unfinished was intentional as I still have a final hurdle to leap over to be fully qualified. Learning and teaching is a never-ending cycle for both pupil and teacher, mostly bouncing both ways like a mirror. The portrait shows a light and a darker side, reflecting the written words used to describe each, positive and negative. The positive representing school experience and the positive traits felt during that time, the act of doing and immersing myself in the role of a teacher and thriving. Whereas, the negative representing the anxious emotion felt during the University setting and the

written assignments which I struggled with. The word 'bittersweet' was used multiple times to demonstrate this juxtaposition.

Fig. 42 End of Placement Evaluation, 2019 (Student E)

This evaluation depicts my personal emotions felt whilst on my last teaching placement. Using text with imagery is something I am extremely passionate about and try to incorporate it into most of my art lessons. I have been going through a fairly traumatic time in my home life which is represented through the glass jar, feeling almost trapped but with potential to break through. During these placements I

met some incredible people (staff and pupils) who brought out the best in me. It felt like family, it felt like home. I was able to be Aoife and laughed again.

The next two figures represent a further example of the use of concept visualisation as applied here to academic reading and writing. This activity involved a group of South Asian teachers working with English as a second language, who were using arts-based methods for the first time, to help them identify (and draw out) the various concepts contained in an academic article (in English) entitled *Inter-professional and inter-agency cooperation: the rough and the smooth* –a core reading on their MSc Education programme in a Scottish University. This activity gave ‘voice’ and ‘agency’ to these non-native English speakers and helped them engage and collaborate with one another in the academic task. Through a process of identifying and drawing-out visual metaphors with chalks, markers and even Lego (Fig. 43) they unpacked this academic article in ways they had never previously been exposed to.

Fig. 43 South Asian teachers (Group A) using arts-based methods to aid their reading of an academic paper

Fig. 44 Another group of South Asian teachers (Group B) using arts-based methods to make visible different metaphors within the academic paper

This group made visible a different section of the academic paper. Here you see evidence of them annotating multi-modally (Kress and Van Leeuwen, 2001) in both written, including in their own native language, and in visual form.

In closing this chapter, I would argue that the journey of research thus far, in terms of aim, ambition and achievement achieves much more than the conclusions suggest in terms of student learning; methods of learning; and theories of learning and in the concluding chapter I will outline very specifically where changes could occur.

CHAPTER 7

RECOMMENDATIONS AND CONCLUDING REMARKS

The following will conclude the work of this thesis, by assessing not just its contribution to the advancement of art in education in Scotland, but also on its wider implications for education and the social sciences more generally.

On *student learning*, the pupils who took part in the research had far more to offer and say than could possibly be assessed by the SQA. Consequently, it is clear from dialoguing with them that they felt hamstrung by the restrictions set by the state examining authority. The modes of assessment were exclusion and did not reflect the methods of our time. For example, the following should not be beyond the reach of the SQA exam board, an assessment incorporating ‘spoken word’ as a method of self-reflection or an ‘online video journal or blog’

As a teacher and researcher, I know that some pupils can better express themselves by talking and allowing for this opportunity to dialogue with your assessor rather than always having to demonstrate one’s knowledge through a written statement or essay.

We know more than we can say as Michael Polanyi argues but we also now know the value of tacit knowing for health and wellbeing purposes as the recent pandemic demonstrated (Polanyi, 2009). Yet there is still no opportunity for pupils to give an oral account of their art learning and its impact on their wellbeing and character (Clarke, 2007). Pupils are constantly being asked to self-evaluate in schools today; yet think for moment how valuable an oral account would be? We know that learning is multifaceted, and especially today with the advancement in technology it is ill-advised to assess work purely based on the SQA’s limiting assessment framework.

On *methods of learning*, it is time to move away from the linearity of traditional skills-based methods of learning in art as taught by state schools and to embrace fully the uncertainty and messiness that ideas-based learning beholds (McAuliffe 2018)

On *theories of learning*, the tools of learning and making in the arts are ever increasing. The arts adopt new methods of meaning making readily because they can – the subject and its material nature allows.

Firstly, a rebalancing of the image/text hierarchy in education is now necessary if we are going to resolve some of the issues raised by this study. Secondly, it is time to dismantle the current framework of dominance in Scottish art education, namely the SQA. Thirdly, it suggests a higher level of thinking in art education must be instituted and past methodologies should be unlearned. A fourth recommendation is to pursue more rigorously the links between art and other subjects is to consider further the opportunities afforded by the STEM-STEAM initiative between the arts and sciences (jagodzinski, 2020). A final recommendation is to avail of the opportunities that have been opened up by two recent reports on Scottish Education, namely the International Council of Educational Advisers (ICEA) 2018, and the OECD, 2021. We now turn to a fuller account of these recommendations.

1. Rebalancing the image/text hierarchy in education

An intention of this research and thesis account has been to highlight that considerable tensions in Scottish art education arise as a result of the inequity caused by the text-based hegemony of our education system (Sousanis, 2015; McAuliffe, 2013, 2018). The primacy of words over images (and sounds) has deep roots in Western culture but what if all these modalities were inextricably linked, and equal partners in meaning making? How the subject is currently examined and graded at National level rests upon an inequity causing an unnecessary tension between these different modes which should otherwise complement each other. Having access to infinite technologies, we now have the means to embrace many modalities, allowing for example, image and text to fully coexist in our art-rooms. A recent visit to a school in Fife, Scotland saw a portraiture class being taught exclusively on iPads, that included both the practical, and the critical and contextual. The ease and pace at which this lesson was conducted raised a number of pedagogical questions for me as a teacher educator, but all pointed to hope rather than fear. This Apple sponsored pilot iPad provision in a number of schools is in effect providing additional teaching and learning time within the subject and this time

could be spent on the critical and contextual aspects of the subject which, as shown in this thesis, catch out so many of our pupils.

2. Dismantling Frameworks of Dominance in Scottish art education

Numerous pedagogical turns and events (Atkinson, 2018; Biesta, 2017; Granville, 2012; Harris, 2014; Heaton, 2021; Humes and Priestly, 2021; Pirrie, 2020) have emerged over the life of the study, including the now almost inevitable 'post pandemic turn' in education.

Stepping back for a moment, it is worth pausing to recall events on that momentous day when the exams were cancelled due to Covid-19 and the impact this moment had for the researcher and the researched (Clough and Nutbrown, 2012; Mishler, 1999; Punch 2005).

On the afternoon of Thursday 19 March 2020, the Scottish Government decided to cancel all school examinations. This was going to be the last occasion where we could engage face to face before the school got organised for 'lockdown' and 'home schooling'. It was therefore necessary that these feedback sessions took place there and then as there was no provision in the initial research agreement with the school for online engagement with the participants, so the alternatives of Zoom or MS Teams were simply not feasible.

On that occasion I happened to be present at my research school to give and receive feedback on the 'case study assemblages' - I had arrived at the school with a full set in A3 paper copies in colour. This feedback exercise needed to occur before the school closed for an unspecified period - this pupil feedback would complete the feedback cycle and their views would be formally recorded to complete the research (Clough and Nutbrown, 2012). In the end, the feedback event was a commitment I had made to the participants at the start of the research project and therefore I had an ethical responsibility to check if the data I had was an accurate record of events (Creswell 2009; Punch 2005; Sikes, 2010).

Examples of the pupil's responses to their 'assemblage' can be viewed below with the remainder archived in Appendix 3

Maura a Secondary 1 (S1) student March 2020 BGE

Questions following the re-presentation of the data in the form of concept visualisations – assemblage

2.0 How do you think the visualisation has captured your understanding of your learning?

I think I like (sic) know how to describe (my learning) it better now. I think you know I know how to shade in stuff and doing it properly, before that I was just doing what the teacher said. I can describe it more in detail and I've learnt more techniques which I can put into my drawing.

2.1 How do you think the visualisation has captured our conversation?

I think I know how to measure it now, like the eyes are too far apart I know how to do it right now and make it look more accurate.

2.3 Is there a place for concept visualisation in art learning?

*I think it's quite good to like describe what you've done but some artwork you can see what's going on...(sic)
It makes sense and you can see how you feel about your artwork and if there is any room to improve. At the beginning I didn't have the terms didn't remember them, but now I do.*

Amira a Secondary 4 (S4) student March 2020 N5

Questions following the re-presentation of the data in the form of concept visualisations (assemblage)

2.0 How do you think the visualisation has captured your understanding of your learning?

It layers the learning and I can read and understand it.

2.1 How do you think the visualisation has captured our conversation?

*I can imagine this in an exhibition
I can see the development of the art and the development of final products and me explaining it.
They would be able to work out the process.
Were you thinking that the image of the trophy matches the idea of being a perfectionist, that's a good point, it had the symmetry so it worked in unifying the overall image.*

2.3 Is there a place for concept visualisation in art learning?

*It makes me stop and pause.
Taking me back to the days when I was making the art. The layers of the text and the art symbolises the layers in the design for example.*

I consider these assemblages works of art and therefore these will eventually be Ink jet printed at the Glasgow Print Studio to museum standards using 308gsm, archival, acid free paper and a copy given to each of the participants. Participants and their families will then be invited to attend a public showing of these 'pedagogical prints' in one of Glasgow Museums' exhibition spaces to be organised in conjunction with the next 'critical pedagogy' seminar that will run as part of Glasgow International festival of visual art in 2023.

I found (as did the participants) the case study assemblage format a very relatable and reliable method in which to recall their learning journey and to discuss again the research with the participants. The case study assemblage methodology as discussed earlier stemmed from my own practice as an artist (Barrett and Bolt, 2010; Sullivan, 2010) so the visualisation process was deeply visceral to me and greatly personal to each of the participants too, given that it was their own artwork I was working with to 'show and tell' their pedagogical story - their meaning makings. Consequently, I was committed to the aesthetic approach (Rose, 2016) I had taken in the presentation of 'findings' and felt these visualisations would accurately represent the research conversations that had taken place (Hickman, 2008)

The fall-out from the announcement that all exams had been cancelled came from the Scottish Cabinet Secretary for Education and Skills, which was played out across the department, was palpable. There was a sense of genuine panic that everything that these pupils had worked for had been taken away from them; a pivotal moment for Scottish Education as nothing like this had ever occurred before. The idea of no exams was disorienting for everyone including the teachers and I as the 'resident researcher' began to trouble the question of what might happen next and what could this mean for the future of Scottish education and especially assessment in art and design. My fieldwork had come to an end and I was now having to make sense of what had just happened. This was a pedagogical event (Atkinson, 2018) like no other and could not be ignored in the final analysis of this project.

Since then Scottish teachers have been working with the SQA's 'pandemic assessment' arrangements for National Qualifications in Art and Design where the

SQA has done what was previously considered unthinkable by allowing art and design exam work to be summatively assessed at its place of making – the art room. (This is common practice elsewhere in the UK where exam boards other than the SQA are responsible.) The SQA assessment arrangements are unique in the UK for the reasons that have been alluded to earlier and so too are the formulaic pedagogies that often precede these assessments (McAuliffe, 2014; 2016).

The disruption caused by the pandemic prompted a radical re-think in respect of assessment and it could be the catalyst for real and sustained change, bringing Scottish school art education into the twenty-first century. Assessment has been the driving force for far too long in Scottish education with scant regard for the question of pedagogy or purpose of education as reported by the recent OECD review of Scottish education (2021).

The idea that teachers might no longer have to concern themselves with such 'utilitarian' tasks as the packaging and transportation of student artwork for assessment by the SQA might have been regarded as a 'game changer' and an unintended consequence of the pandemic. Yet on a recent visit back to the school where the research was conducted I engaged in some follow-up discussion with colleagues and enquired how the 'teacher assessments' had gone. Much to my surprise, teachers proceeded to outline the near trauma that many of them had felt at having to switch roles from being a supportive teacher to being their pupils' assessor. There was a widespread perception that the teacher's new role as assessor had 'betrayed the student-teacher relationship' that they had spent years fostering. Atkinson would describe this as an 'event' (Atkinson, 2018) for which the possibility of change was for now, at the very least, possible.

Just recently, the academic Mark Priestly who is Director of the Sterling Network for Curriculum Studies at Sterling University and an outspoken critic of the Scottish Government's curriculum reforms (Humes and Priestley, 2021) provided further evidence of the need for a shift in emphasis from 'skills-based' to 'ideas-based' thinking in Scottish education. Writing on Twitter in May 2021 in response to a leak of SQA National 5 and Higher exam papers on the TikTok social media platform, Priestley used the occasion to advance the following view on assessment, which is

worthy of repeating here in full:

'A test or exam where pupils can bring notes etc. Where the ability to work with *ideas* is more important than recall. Less of an issue if topic/question known in advance. *We need to rethink assessment*' (@MarkRPriestley 7/5/2021 16.06 Twitter) (emphasis mine)

The 'assemblages' are a visualisation of that pedagogic shift in dialogue. This shift would enable a greater diversity of work to be presented for assessment such as site specific, issue-based and time-based pieces. This would be transformative for the subject and dialogically it would open it up to other disciplines, an aspect that will be explored below, in the section on *Interdisciplinarity: Reframing the Dialogue between Arts and Sciences*. It would also mean that Scottish 'school art' would no longer need to be defined by its distinctively restrictive form and size (A3), and maybe finally, 'ideas-based thinking' might begin to permeate a critical art making where 'critical ideas are given visual form' (Atkinson and Dash, 2005; xii Somerson and Hermano, 2013).

Breaking from the formulaic practices of the past and present could help move the subject towards embedding a form of 'Studio Thinking' (Hetland, et al 2013) - a pedagogic approach delivered in a number of States in the US and in the Scottish Highlands. See page 95 where this practice is further explored.

In the early days of CfE, when it was first implemented back in 2010 there was an aspiration to change the way art was assessed, with suggestions that it should be done locally and moderated regionally. These arrangements, unfortunately, never came to pass and the system has retained its centralising control; that is, until the pandemic hit.

There is no doubt that this centralising control limits student agency and constrains what is possible in the here and now (Humes and Priestley, 2021). Not everything that is possible in school art can be packaged and shipped for assessment. The subject needs to find a 'home' again (Thomson and Hall, 2021) and be allowed to grow and develop in meaningful and critical ways, and be supported by an

examinations framework that is open to the range of diverse practices such as those signalled in the case study assemblages.

I end this section with Gert Biesta's plea against taking art in education for granted and pointing to an emergent culture of 'instrumentalism' as in this case of the SQA where '...the potential disappearance of art from art education' (Biesta, 2017:53) is a real possibility, where art is placed in the service of other disciplines or removed altogether. This was the route proposed by Michael Gove, England's former education secretary in his pursuit of the English Baccalaureate (TES, 2016), a curriculum without the arts.

3 Reinstating Cognition: studio thinking, latency, unknowing and deep learning.

Fig.45 Too easy – A Room 13 participant at the entrance to the original Studio, at Caol Primary School, Fort William, with her work inspired by the artist Ruth Ewan ‘Nae Sums’ - a UWS Artist Teacher – Room 13 joint project for Glasgow International 2012 (Photo: courtesy of Room 13 International).

Hernandez-Hernandez (2019: 60) draws our attention to the ‘pedagogical imagination’ which, he argues, ‘affords us the capacity to invent, experiment and create, isolated from routines and trends’. This research project has certainly given me similar affordances, enabling me to challenge the *status quo* in the manner of the pupils in Room 13 who found mainstream education ‘too easy’ (Fig.40) a point that is underpinned by the recent the OECD (2021) review of *Curriculum for Excellence*.

Pupils' perceived inability to articulate their learning in art along with the high failure rate of the 'question paper' at National 5 (SQA) gave rise to much of the impetus for this study. It felt as though these concerns needed to be worked through and made visible as they have been in the 'assemblages'. Accordingly, the disconnect between image and text or, to put it more accurately, between image making and writing, is what lies at the heart of this concern. The 'siloes' nature of current subject teaching in Scotland has become detrimental to art learning. It is only when we learn to 'cross boundaries' (McAuliffe 2018; Giroux, 1993) that we can begin to make sense of our world and engage in future work beyond the classroom (Pirrie, 2020).

Rebecca Heaton in her seminal paper on 'Cognition in art education' states that

...cognitive connections require visualisation and recognition in art education because they join personal, professional, social and cultural habitats (Bourdieu, 1984; Burnard et al., 2016). (Heaton, 2021:4)

All of the case study assemblages from S1 -S6 reveal some or all of Heaton's 'cognitive connections'. These connections can cause tensions in the secondary school art department when meaning making goes unsupported because of a lack of expertise. This problem could be mitigated by working more closely with other non-art or text-based subjects such as the Sciences and English.

The last fourteen years of CfE have proven that despite the existence of a liberating set of permissions granted to teachers in the form of the policy document *Creativity 3-18* produced by Education Scotland in 2007, the fear of failure and lack of creative infrastructure such as that offered by the SQA meant that those creative opportunities were lost or at best rarely sought.

As I have argued elsewhere (McAuliffe, 2016; 2018) that the current modus operandi of the SQA is far too centralised. The assessment of art and design in one location affirms a worrying anxiety for the 'absolute' control of standards and grades rather than a flipping of the pedagogy and giving the agency and professional judgement to teachers.

Humes and Priestly (2021:186) reminds us that:

‘...one of the stated intentions of CfE was to encourage teachers to take more responsibility and exercise greater agency in their professional work’

The pedagogy that follows a culture of control is always going to be constrained with its limiting scope for creativity and experimentation as evident throughout the majority of the country’s secondary art departments (McAuliffe, 2016). Yet, as earlier mentioned, such notable pedagogical practices have managed to emerge in recent times in some regions of the United States, namely through Studio Thinking (Hetland, et al 2013). Studio thinking embraces a range of pedagogies that mainstream art education in Scotland or the wider UK have not acknowledged bar one or two exceptions. Where this studio thinking is in place they encourage what are known as Studio Habits of Mind (ibid). These ‘habits’ are not unlike the dispositions engendered by Room 13 (fig 39)– a studio enterprise model of teaching developed in the Scottish Highlands (Gibb, 2012; Adams and Owens, 2015). This way of thinking and making has developed ‘habits’ around the concepts of ‘persistence’, ‘reflection’ and ‘envisioning’ to mention just a few (ibid). These dispositions reflect very closely how artist-teacher pedagogies are nurtured where such opportunities exist (Daichendt, 2010).

Arguably, ‘studio thinking’ best describes the kind of pedagogy I was modelling with the case study assemblages, namely hanging-out around ideas in a studio or lab like environment. These assemblages have served to document and demonstrate a depth and complexity of conversations which took place over the course of the research where tolerance (Freire, 1996), latency and difficulty (Meyer and Land 2006) were brought to the fore and allowed to become ‘visible’. The pupils did not possess the language to allow any great discussion, but through ‘indirection’ they found their utterances and became more willing to articulate. It is this kind of disposition that helps the preservation of ambiguity, difference and critical thinking in art making. And these ‘cognitive connections’ (Heaton, 2021) make for great art and tend not to result in formulaic but rather in genuine critical art making.

It is also this hanging-out in liminal spaces (both real and imagined) that were central to my conversations with the pupils during my field research. This hanging out was always relational as their artwork was always present. It was *their* art work which

focused the discussions and maintained the discursive complexities. It is their artwork that remains central to meaning-making in the assemblages.

Jane Speedy's (2015) 'staring' methodology was usefully applied here as I sat with pupils in front of their artwork while we tried to work out what just happened in terms of their learning. The answers lay in the artwork itself, as argued earlier (Hickman, 2008). Staring at their artwork as we did for durations of 5-10 minutes at a time, before the 'assemblage' was even generated provided the necessary resonances which in turn provided a narrative aid to communicate one's thoughts and learnings.

This research has identified through the assemblages that there is a visceral desire to be 'in relation' to studio work itself when trying to articulate one's learning. The degree to which we begin to speak more fluently in and through the making is beyond question. The case study assemblages speak for themselves and make visible those difficult-to-describe, troublesome areas of learning in art education (Meyer and Land, 2006) which we need to encourage and sustain.

I find agreement with Dias and Fernandez, in their description of that latency or reflective dimension that has unfortunately been driven out of school art in Scotland. They argue:

'...knowing and not knowing function as parts of the same movement of existence that does not separate singularity from plurality, real from virtual; past from future, subject from object or self from otherness' (Dias and Fernandez, 2019:138).

In a similar vein Baldacchino (2019, xii) argues for embracing our otherness as a precondition for unlearning. That is to say, we must be prepared to 'stay the distance' for renewal to occur and unlearning to take place. He argues:

'Unlearning the certainties by which we were schooled also urges us to enter into the world of possibilities. To do so we have to embrace paradox, as we seek to unlearn what we know without presuming to relearn other certainties or find new canons on which we would secure a measurable outcome' (Baldacchino, 2019, xii)

Finally, we should allow our pupils to use whatever means they have to express themselves without having to fit in with externally imposed restrictions that are now out of step with our times. The Covid-19 pandemic served to disrupt the SQA's long serving practice of centralising the assessment of art. It is hoped at the very least

that the removal of very limiting size restrictions on artworks will help give rise to a new 'school art' for Scotland.

4. Interdisciplinarity: Reframing the Dialogue between Arts and Sciences

The fourth significant observation stemming from this research is the realisation that we urgently need to move away from what was earlier identified as 'silo thinking' where art speaks only to itself, a point identified in Donaldson's review of Scottish teacher education *Teaching Scotland's Future* way back in 2010 and again referred to by Humes and Priestley in 2021 suggesting that this recommendation was never enacted.

Evidently those who have examined education in recent times (Donaldson, 2010; Humes and Priestley, 2021, Biesta, 2015) would agree with this move towards what Petrie has referred to as 'the desirability of the integration of knowledge into some meaningful whole' (Petrie, 1992 in Burnard; Colucci-Gray and Sinha, 2021). It is this 'meaningful whole' that the case study assemblages tried to capture aesthetically in order to make visible the phenomenon of integrated learning that embraces the whole person. Fig. 47 is illustrative of the kind of understandings that is generated when the arts and sciences are put to work on a problem. In Fig.46, the art and science students are making *visible* the science of colour blindness. One group of student teachers were simply curious as to what colour blindness was so half the group being art trained and the other half science trained set to work on trying to gain an understanding of this phenomena. The art students had no scientific understanding of the phenomena and so the science students explained in simple terms what happens to the composition of the brain when colour blindness occurs.

Fig. 46 The Art and Science of Colour: from STEM to STEAM case studies, PGDE Art and Science Secondary Teacher Education students present their findings.

Burnard and Colucci-Gray (2020) make a timely and compelling case for interdisciplinarity and working across boundaries in education. As a teacher educator, especially now in this post pandemic period, when time and content relevance seem more pressing than ever, I feel I have a moral and political responsibility (Giroux, 1993) to make the case for interdisciplinarity and to advance its relevance to art education in this, the third decade of the century.

In the opening chapter of 'Why science and art creativities matter...' Pirrie posits the following explanation for why reframing the dialogue between Arts and Sciences is so necessary:

Reconceptualising the interrelationship between sciences and the arts has the potential to bring us back from a different planet as it were. It is only by considering the arts and sciences from the inside rather than as reified categories that can be progressively realigned that we shall be better able to inhabit the Earth and to address the many challenges that we currently face (2020: 21).

In this multi-modal world (Kress and van Leeuwen 2006), which we inhabit, it is foolhardy to continue to see art as an entirely separate subject rather than part of the wider set of disciplines associated with STEAM education. The STEM to STEAM movement in Scotland is in its infancy with barely a mention on the Education Scotland government site (McKinnon et al, 2022) Furthermore, during these past 18 months which have given rise to a serious Health and Wellbeing crisis for society, the arts have helped get people through it in various ways (Payne, 2020).

Undoubtedly, the expressive arts curriculum now needs to be re-evaluated and at least some additional curricular time needs to be apportioned for its work in meeting many of the needs of mental wellbeing within the Health and Wellbeing curriculum.

Mental wellbeing in the Scottish Curriculum refers to:

...the health of the mind, the way we think, perceive, reflect on and make sense of the world (Scottish Executive, 2004a)

According to the *Curriculum for Excellence*, the current Health and Wellbeing curriculum excludes the arts with the exception of dance. This omission now needs to be reframed in light of what we know the arts have achieved during the pandemic. Arguably, learning knows no boundaries and art connects everything; so where there is a desire to see a solution, art can help us 'see it' as it is the job of art to make things visible (Hofsess, Riddett, and Siegesmund 73: 2019).

When set against the hard sciences (STEM) the arts feel subordinated yet when they work in partnership with each other in equal dialogue as we did in the STEM to STEAM project it's collegiate and discursive from the moment of engagement. It is too often that we read of the conflict inherent in the art-science binary. It's divisive yet this divide exists in most schools.

The interdisciplinary theme of colour was mutually agreed as a theme worth exploring between the subjects of art and science. I had previous experience working with science colleagues at another institution making colour by extracting dyes from vegetation; the dye was then used for expressive purposes.

That intellectual space or 'oxygen' as I prefer to call it that is generated from our interactions with other disciplines especially in the sciences should by now be

considered mainstream in education. How for example do you begin to understand the notion of 'colour-blindness' without first understanding the concept in *both* arts and science?

The same dynamic is true for 'game design' where art and design has a vast stake in that industry yet despite the high levels of engagement, we know students to have when involved in 'gaming' it is still not considered in Scotland as part of the art and design school curriculum. jagodzinski argues:

The process of designing and game thinking for non-gaming contexts as a way to engage students and solve problems is perceived as leading to more engagement by students in schools...gamification in education is touted as a key 21 st-century approach to learning (2020:17).

Fig. 47 From STEM to STEAM. UWS PGDE Art and Science teacher education students explore the art and science of perception and the human eye.

5. Teachers as Curriculum Developers and Change Agents

The fifth recommendation stemming from this study is to envision a curriculum where teachers feel that they *are* curriculum developers and change agents. The case study assemblages helped provide me with the necessary data to enable a shift in the dialogue towards a more critical curricular meaning making.

When Humes and Priestly (2021) advocate ‘agency’ in relation to Scottish Education, what is being proposed is indeed a request for *radical reform* of its current frameworks and anything less will fail to deliver on their aspirations to see teachers as ‘curriculum developers’ and ‘change agents’ (Humes and Priestly, 2021:176).

Like ‘working from home’ and the adjustments we all needed to make for this to work during the pandemic, we can do the same in terms of realigning current arts practices and assessment. There is an *agentive* opportunity here which if embraced could work to make teachers the ‘curriculum developers and change agents’ (Humes and Priestly, 2021:176) that CfE had always intended would happen but never did.

Scotland is fortuitous however, in having an outward facing administration which values education. Education is held in high regard by Scots, they have always ‘owned it’ unlike other aspects of governance in the devolved arrangements at the Scottish Parliament. This, however, has not always boded well for art education as the pace of change is never quick enough. It appears that the system is not nearly responsive enough and having a single exam board responsible for assessment in state schools does not incentivise pace or change (McAuliffe, in Hepburn, 2020)

The Scottish Government recently decided, after much political wrangling about the ‘attainment gap’ (in literacy and numeracy) and its failure to close it over the last fourteen years (Humes and Priestly, 2021) to finally subject CfE to international review by the International Council of Educational Advisers (ICEA, 2018). This review cautions against the language of delivery and states that a

‘clear and consistent narrative of change’ is needed: that narrative ‘should be founded on professional agency, empowerment, improvement and change, and not on the technical terminology of delivery, reform and implementation’ (ICEA,2018:186).

There was mention of the Regional Improvement Collaboratives (RICs) and that these should be 'contextually nuanced and contextually embedded' (ibid,187).

This concluding remark from the ICEA underpins much of the thinking established in this research and therefore provides a hopeful narrative for the future of Scottish Art Education.

In Conclusion

This research bound within my own professional doctorate journey and informal reflection set out to explore how using narrative and arts-based methods vis-à-vis the case study assemblages might uncover and make visible the complex nature of art learning thus enabling pupils to articulate better their learning. It chose to adopt a method of enquiry that was primarily art-based (Hickman, 2008) and because of this the project was considered relevant and useful to both staff and pupils of the research school. That is, to explore together how staff, students and myself could see how this research might help to position if not advance their subject within the hierarchy of the school. The department's very first STEM – STEAM event in the form of a fashion show occurred around this time of this is now an annual occurrence.

I endeavoured to remain outside what Baldacchino (2019: 80) refers to as '...the boundaries of methodological dogma and procedural measurement'. I did so by resisting a move towards any ideology including the 'lure' of a/r/t/ography (Springgay and Irwin, 2005). Though the methodologies used in this study borrow much from a/r/t/ography, I instead found a 'secure' home in the 'thinking spaces' occupied by the subject of art in education itself (Atkinson, D. 2018; Hickman, R. 2005).

The 'ineffable' and 'unknowing' did not unfortunately appear in the lexicon of the pupils' learning, and it is time it did. Nonetheless, the concepts of 'accuracy' and 'certainty' did feature especially in relation to the language of the SQA assessments. Such language is still used to describe approaches to drawing and the presentation of work for assessment and this continues to resonate in art departments today.

This staff at the research school did however mitigate the SQA's demands and in the end afforded the pupils a genuine expressive arts education, subverting the exams protocols where possible to benefit the pupils (Humes, and Priestley, 2021). The case of Ava (Assemblage VII) is a good example where staff accommodated the student on her own terms to get her through her National Qualifications.

In addition to these limitations pupils have to deal with the SQA's restriction on paper size for exam submissions (as earlier mentioned). However luckily these restrictions were also mitigated by the staff who did all they could to engage the pupils in a genuine and authentic practice at the broad general education (BGE) stage of their education (Secondary 1-3) where exam rules do not apply.

Using exemplification from their own practice as creatives whilst at the same time meeting the requirements of their exam board (SQA). Pupils were taken through the fine art and design making processes that they as staff had experienced in art school and it was no surprise to note that all members of staff were well qualified in their individual art and design specialisms, all having graduated from the country's top ranking art schools.

I have shown through this study that there is an alternative way in which art can be presented and assessed within state schools in Scotland that ensures not just its survival as a subject domain within the school curriculum but that

There needs to be a concerted effort to realign the subject and to shift the focus away from its traditional single trajectory of preparing pupils for art school.

The research I presented vis-vis the 'assemblages' tell a very particular story of how each individual pupil engages with assessment. It is a complex story of learning that I believe is best presented using the assemblage method.

There are implications for the wider social sciences too as we all rely increasingly on visual methods to communicate complex ideas.

The arts provide an embodied message that can be eloquently and aesthetically communicated. This refocus would give the subject greater meaning and increase its appeal as a serious subject that matters to this century and our time.

In Finland they are fostering subject cooperation over competition by pushing for abandonment of 'school subjects' (HED 2022) perhaps this strategy could provide the subject of art and design with the direction it now needs.

A direction which reflects the 'visual narrative turn' along with the 'pedagogic turn' to art as research that I have demonstrated throughout this study (Harris, 2014; Sullivan, 2010; Granville, 2012).

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Appendices

Appendix 1. An account of the pre-module stages of the DProf.

Appendix 2. Interview schedule

Appendix 3. Interview transcripts

Appendix 4. Letters to Director of Education and Head Teacher

Appendix 5. Informed Consent Form

Appendix 6. Participant Information Sheets for Adult and Child

Appendix 7. Examples of Autoethnography – Narrative Inquiry

Appendix 8. Examples of Concept Visualisation

Appendix 9. Self-Portrait, Gillard (2018)

Appendix 10. Observation and interview timetable at the Research School

Appendix 11. Whiteboard Thinking: initial ‘thinking out’ of the project at the University of Bristol

Appendix 1

The following is an account of the pre-module stages of the DProf. These were undertaken at the University of Bristol (2013-18); the final stage (the *dissertation stage*) I decided to transfer to my home institution at UWS. In describing these modules, I have in some cases draw on the assignment associated with the module to outline its content.

1. Understanding Educational Research
2. Narrative Inquiry
3. Auto Ethnography
4. Writing for Inquiry
5. Narrative Interviewing
6. Visual Inquiry
7. Preparation for Dissertation

1. Understanding Educational Research

The focus of this core overarching module was an invitation to critically explore the philosophical underpinnings of research, specifically the epistemological and ontological assumptions that underlie different research traditions. What became clear whilst engaging in this module is that the field of educational research as with any other fields of human endeavour, is fundamentally complex and that it is therefore rarely a case of choosing one research paradigm over another but rather recognising that '(t)he distinctions *within* the so-called paradigms are often as significant as the distinctions between them' (Pring, 2004:48) (emphasis his). The idea that research in education was 'guided more by government policy and social administration than by intellectual critique' was also a surprise to me in my formative years as a lecturer and beginning researcher (Delanty, 1997:29). Suffice to say that on reflection as a beginning researcher I was in denial of the complexity of the field of research methods and this module helped me overtake that simplistic position. In short, I believed then as I do now that most research could and should be approached from the hermeneutic/interpretivist/critical theory tradition. The module also included an input on Research Ethics for Social Sciences

2. Narrative Inquiry

This module critiqued ‘narrative’ as a root metaphor for understanding describing human experience. It provided me with an overview of contemporary narrative research and helped me to develop a critical awareness of the implications and positions of particular methodological choices. I engaged in structured activities that required me to compare and evaluate specific narrative approaches to research.

3. Auto Ethnography

This module deepened my understanding of how we differentiate between autobiographical, auto/biographical and auto ethnographic research and focused on the latter – an ethnographic genre using my own life experience as part of the ‘field of study’. I considered the ethical and aesthetic dimensions to these writing genres and explored the ways in which auto-ethnographic texts highlight the relationship between cultures and agencies.

4. Writing for Inquiry

This module was about writing your way deep *into* the subject of your inquiry; that inquiry is represented here in the thesis by a single photograph taken of my office window and features at the start of Chapter 4. The following narrative best describes what I was *doing* in this module. Effectively, I was learning to write using a particular narrative method.

The image before me, photographed at my place of work, consists of a series of virtual and real spaces, which I have been playing with vis-à-vis arranging and rearranging in my mind’s eye, as if these particular spaces were demanding to be shaped, assembled and articulated. After all, it was just a random photograph. Yet, complexity of form is writ large and crystal clear; although, until the point of inquiry it remains amorphous and without signification. Inquiry interrogates, Inquiry opens up previously concealed spaces, in previously unknowable zones.

I took strength from *The Collected Writings of Joe Brainard* (2012) for this assignment.

5. Narrative Interviewing

This module introduced me to the key concepts in narrative research interviewing including the gathering, selection, transcription and co-construction of life stories and personal and group narratives within interviews and conversations. Experiential activities provided opportunities to explore interviewer positions and conversational styles. Input, debate and discussions equipped me to identify and evaluate appropriate interview strategies and practices suitable to my project. Here I was introduced to the interview methods of Elliot Mishler (1996) whose work, was, in the end, core to my research.

6. Visual Inquiry

The initial *doing* of this module was premised within a theoretical framework that drew on a range of theories from education (Dewey, 2009; Bruner, 1996), aesthetics (Bachelard, 1994; Wittgenstein, 2015) to wider field of philosophy. The depth of attentiveness (Springgay, Irwin, 2005) given to the *making of art* as presented in the assessed performative paper that accompanied this module, was I

would argue an example of visual inquiry at its most visceral, however that attentiveness did not translate into any meaningful written narrative that could ultimately be 'put on display' (Mitchell, 2002:166) to generate this new curricular meaning making that I was seeking. I remain hopeful that through this study I can shift beyond the binary of writing and/or art making and arrive at some other coherent plateau (Speedy, 2015). In this paper, consideration has been given, though not 'uncritically' to 'a/r/tography' as one possible 'way-out' of the latter problem. Springgay, Irwin, (2005: 904) have over recent years been telling us that 'a/r/tography' can provide the necessary 'attentiveness to what is seen and known and to what lies beneath the surface' of art making.

7. Preparation for Dissertation

This module afforded me the opportunity to explore through 'articulation' in the widest sense the nature of my 'dissertation' topic. It introduced me to various forms of dissertation including the 'visual essay' which was new to me and influenced me to ultimately take on a hybrid approach to my dissertation.

Appendix 2

Interview schedule

Questions following a period of close observation by the researcher

- 1.0 Can you describe what you are doing right now?
- 1.1 Can you talk me through your process of your art-making? (How have you made this?)
- 1.2 What was the most difficult aspect of your making?
- 1.3 What was the least difficult aspect?
- 1.4 What do you hope to learn by making this? (What is the range of knowledge and skills in arts-practice?)
- 1.5 What knowledge and skills do you hope to achieve?
- 1.6 What knowledge and skills are valued by you?
- 1.7 What knowledge and skills are valued by the school?
- 1.8 Do you have the subject-specific language to enable you to verbally articulate your learning?
- 1.9 Do learners need to be able to describe their learning (in verbal and written modes) and if so what are the benefits?

Questions following the re-presentation of the data in the form of concept visualisations (assemblage)

- 2.0 How do you think the visualisation has captured your understanding of your learning?
- 2.1 How do you think the visualisation has captured our conversation?
- 2.2 Is there a place for concept visualisation in art learning?

Appendix 3

Interview transcripts

Maura a Secondary 1 (S1) student March 2020 BGE

1.0 Can you describe what you are doing right now?

So, we've been making self-portraits but would been taking it part at a time. So right now been doing the eyes so the first thing we did was we drew across and then we did kind of units of measurement so this would be a new this (pointing to her finger) altogether your face with five units and then you draw box around where what what size your faces yesterday we were starting on our eyes. Looking at the shape of our eyes in the mirror trying to get them to look at the same as possible so you draw the shape of your eye and then you draw the iris in the black bit

Then we drew the eyebrows which is on the top side of the circle

1.1 Can you talk me through your process of your art-making? (How have you made this?)

1.2 What was the most difficult aspect of your making?

Trying to get them to look the same

1.3 What was the least difficult aspect?

Probably doing the units as it was simple and she got talked through it, it didn't have to be too precise.

1.4 What do you hope to learn by making this? (What is the range of knowledge and skills in arts-practice?) *Maybe trying to learn to do an accurate self-portrait so I tried to before all these techniques it looks like a different person [do we still need to draw the face out that we have cameras]*

I think it's quite good because it can kind of relaxes you

Like with a camera you can just think about its not really the same as just drawing it you feel better about you can kind of entertain you. On the phone you can just take it but with this you can be happy in yourself you can see it's all finished and stuff.

1.5 What knowledge and skills do you hope to achieve?

1.6 What knowledge and skills are valued by you?

Probably ammm will I don't really know

You can look you can make yourself look like cartoon if you take your time when you do all the detail it will look more like you.

1.7 What knowledge and skills are valued by the school?

Probably like know, probably the units of measurement

Doesn't have to be exact precise can still make you make look similar

1.8 Do you have the subject-specific language to enable you to verbally articulate your learning?

We haven't really learnt that much language - we can still describe it

1.9 Do learners need to be able to describe their learning (in verbal and written modes) and if so what are the benefits?

I feel it is kind of important

It depends on what it is. I actually think the painting is more important than describing!

Questions following the re-presentation of the data in the form of concept visualisations – assemblage

2.0 How do you think the visualisation has captured your understanding of your learning?

I think I like (sic) know how to describe (my learning) it better now. I think you know I know how to shade in stuff and doing it properly, before that I was just doing what the teacher said. I can describe it more in detail and I've learnt more techniques which I can put into my drawing.

2.1 How do you think the visualisation has captured our conversation?

I think I know how to measure it now, like the eyes are too far apart I know how to do it right now and make it look more accurate.

2.3 Is there a place for concept visualisation in art learning?

I think it's quite good to like describe what you've done but some artwork you can see what's going on...(sic)

It makes sense and you can see how you feel about your artwork and if there is any room to improve. At the beginning I didn't have the terms didn't remember them, but now I do.

Chen a Secondary 1 (S1) student March 2020 BGE

1.0 Can you describe what you are doing right now?

We are drawing ourself. So like we use our finger to measure ourselves and then yeah. We are working on drawing our eyes right now yeah.

1.1 Can you talk me through your process of your art-making? (How have you made this?) *So we draw a straight line across and then we draw a line across then we put our finger here then we start to measure and then we mark our lines and then and then we mark our line you be half and half. Then you draw the line that you mark down.*

1.2 What was the most difficult aspect of your making?

I think it's just drawing the eyes and nose and the mouth quite difficult to do.

1.3 What was the least difficult aspect?

Well, we are only have work on our eyes so far...

1.4 What do you hope to learn by making this? (What is the range of knowledge and skills in arts-practice?) *Like I know how to draw like a person and yeah and you learn things. Like we used to just draw random.*

1.5 What knowledge and skills do you hope to achieve?

That I know how to measure my face where do I put my eyes and nose.

1.6 What knowledge and skills are valued by you?

I think it's quite important quite good use

1.7 What knowledge and skills are valued by the school?

1.8 Do you have the subject-specific language to enable you to verbally articulate your learning?

1.9 Do learners need to be able to describe their learning (in verbal and written modes) and if so what are the benefits?

1.0 Can you describe what you are doing right now?

So we've been doing a portrait. I have been looking in the mirror to see our features. And we've been doing it so it's more exact because a lot of us are drawing it a bit cartoony. So to get it more realistic and to get the exact proportions really of your face.

.1.1 Can you talk me through your process of your art-making? (How have you made this?)

So what I did I halved it to get the middle point. And then I put a line across the paper use your fingers from measurements and just where the knuckle is is one measurement and we did 5 along and 3.5 up that's how we measured the proportions. And we drew circle to get our eyes and then we looked closely at our eyes to see what shape they are.

1.2 What was the most difficult aspect of your making?

Probably getting in the eyes right because they're quite hard do right but that just shows where you need to practice.

1.3 What was the least difficult aspect? *It's probably just doing the measurements because you just use your fingers and it's easy to fix your mistakes and things like that it's just easier really.*

1.4 What do you hope to learn by making this? (What is the range of knowledge and skills in arts-practice?)

To get the right proportions drawing my face and to improve from my previous portrait. And To take away the skills that I can do this without any help. Just as an aside do you think we still need to draw in this way given that we have cameras? Yeah because you know cameras (...) drawing is a skill we need to do, I would like to do.

Why?

Knowing that you're doing is really. like if I take a picture it's the phone doing all the work. But if I'm drawing it I know in myself I done it the Drawing (sic)

1.5 What knowledge and skills do you hope to achieve?

Some self-confidence in knowing new can do this and that's the main thing for me.

1.6 What knowledge and skills are valued by you?

1.7 What knowledge and skills are valued by the school?

I think they are looking for improvement in your drawings just in the whole that you're drawing better improving because that's all they can for really.

1.8 Do you have the subject-specific language to enable you to verbally articulate your learning?

I think I'm still improving ...but am I still need to learn some vocabulary. Have you learnt any new words Not particularly but I think I will for sure.

1.9 Do learners need to be able to describe their learning (in verbal and written modes) and if so what are the benefits? *I think am just being able talk about your learning means you know what you're doing hundred percent and it's good to be able to talk about what you're learning.*

Lewis S1

To learn to draw in perspective because that can be used in many ways.

Draw in 2D and 3D – to make it more realistic

To be able to draw things in 3D is a good skill

That you understand it and that you understand why this is helping you.

The value knowing that you progressing.

If you know how to speak about it, it means you really do know what you are doing!

Questions following the re-presentation of the data in the form of concept visualisations (assemblage)

2.0 How do you think the visualisation has captured your understanding of your learning?

Do you recognise this? Does it capture your learning?

I recognise the face and everything...

I put together your drawings and the things you said to make this image/assemblage of your learning so that you can see the learning

2.1 How do you think the visualisation has captured our conversation?

It totally reflects it

2.3 Is there a place for concept visualisation in art learning and to meditate on your learning.

Absolutely, the necessity to see a problem that's what this was about... to meditate

Jason a Secondary 2 (S2) student March 2020 BGE

1.0 Can you describe what you are doing right now?

1.1 Can you talk me through your process of your art-making? (How have you made this?)

Well, we first started to learn... Space out the face

Then we worked on drawing the actual parts of the face the eyes and the nose in the mouth and the hair... and then we worked on how to draw down properly

1.2 What was the most difficult aspect of your making?

Probably for me it was the nose and the mouth and the eyebrows. I'm just not very good at drawing people

1.3 What was the least difficult aspect?

Perhaps the dimensions easy to remember I quite enjoy drawing the eye.

1.4 What do you hope to learn by making this? (What is the range of knowledge and skills in arts-practice?)

1.5 What knowledge and skills do you hope to achieve?

Mainly how to draw a face... and how to space at the drawing of the face

1.6 What knowledge and skills are valued by you?

Personally, I find it very valuable to know how to draw.

1.7 What knowledge and skills are valued by the school?

Learning and achieving the best you can and following it what you want to do

1.8 Do you have the subject-specific language to enable you to verbally articulate your learning?

I think so.

1.9 Do learners need to be able to describe their learning (in verbal and written modes) and if so what are the benefits?

It's not as important as learning in the first place.

Jo a Secondary 2 (S2) student March 2020 BGE

1.0 Can you describe what you are doing right now?

Well, all you were researching famous architects for a project we are going to be doing.

1.1 Can you talk me through your process of your art-making? (How have you made this?) *So, the first time we came into art we did first drawing without any practice or anything. And throughout the time we started looking at different details the eyes nose and mouth. So, whereabouts on the face you would put stuff. So, in the end you could see the difference between you between your first portrait and your last one which was much better.*

1.2 What was the most difficult aspect of your making?

Probably just learning to do something you're not used to doing.

1.3 What was the least difficult aspect?

Probably the fact that it was explained easily you could pick it up.

1.4 What do you hope to learn by making this? (What is the range of knowledge and skills in arts-practice?) *Just like to see and prove what you could do better.*

1.5 What knowledge and skills do you hope to achieve?

Just to improve you see we did stuff like look at a mirror and picking up details.

1.6 What knowledge and skills are valued by you?

Learning details because I feel that you could transfer to different things. We learned this to finger trick two fingers from the ear and different layouts that she could do that could be brought into if I'm drawing something in 'tech'.

1.7 What knowledge and skills are valued by the school?

Just focusing in on there is no pressure or anything you just competing against yourself.

1.8 Do you have the subject-specific language to enable you to verbally articulate your learning?

No, I wouldn't say so naw! I don't think I would. I am not very good at having to explain.

1.9 Do learners need to be able to describe their learning (in verbal and written modes) and if so what are the benefits?

I would say probably yes because if you are explaining what you're doing it's another way of showing that you know it.

Jessica a Secondary 2 (S2) student March 2020 BGE

Jessica S2

Doing a portrait (remember most vividly)

Not very good at drawing faces – people

Good at plants

To know how to space out a drawing of the face (I value this)

I find it very valuable to know how to be able to draw a mouth and a nose

Learning through doing (Practice rather than theory)

To be able to verbally explain your work is important.

It means other people can get an idea of what you are doing

Gaudi inspired **Headpiece** based on his buildings Helps you find inspiration in different things...

Art and science (architecture) I like the sound of this as a job as it requires art and science.

Got multiply pictures of Gaudi's buildings and started sketching

No diary of words taken as such

We forget words if we don't use them

Coming up with a design was difficult

Questions following the re-presentation of the data in the form of concept visualisations (assemblage)

2.0 How do you think the visualisation has captured your understanding of your learning?

Its nice to look at the things I was thinking of when making these drawings

2.1 How do you think the visualisation has captured our conversation?

Yes, I stand by it!

2.3 Is there a place for concept visualisation in art learning?

Yes, because it's a form of art.

Ava a Secondary 2 (S3) student March 2020 N5

1.0 Can you describe what you are doing right now?

We making pom-pom garlands to sell at the Christmas fair

1.1 Can you talk me through your process of your art-making? (How have you made this?)

So we are making box characters to go into a board game

So in another class we are drawing objects shading them.

So what are we looking at here?

These are just my dealings

I do them anywhere I go. I don't know I just do work comes into my head.

Do you know toothless? I do whatever comes into my head.

My method is madness, ah. chaotic madness, it channels into the pencil and goes all over the sheet.

1.2 What was the most difficult aspect of your making?

Trying to explain what is. And probably getting proportions rights. Just to the new and.... and not getting it right and leaving it for a couple of days.

1.3 What was the least difficult aspect?

Thinking about it I am very creative in my mind

1.4 What do you hope to learn by making this? (What is the range of knowledge and skills in arts-practice?)

I don't know may be creativity are just trying to get its on paper

And what's your understanding of creativity

Creativity can be anything it doesn't really have a boundary it can be basically anything that you can show.

1.5 What knowledge and skills do you hope to achieve?

Just having fun. And getting what's in my head onto paper

1.6 What knowledge and skills are valued by you?

I don't know I don't know how you are anything it's just fun

1.7 What knowledge and skills are valued by the school?

I don't know what they would value I'm not really sure if its creativity or not, the thing is mainly trying to get a good mark.

1.8 Do you have the subject-specific language to enable you to verbally articulate your learning?

I don't think anyone can have all those words because I can be anything anybody wanted to be and just trying to have fun and trying to get to art school can do well.

It's completely different. I think in other subjects

1.9 Do learners need to be able to describe their learning (in verbal and written modes) and if so what are the benefits?

I can tell people what I'm doing and how are I'm doing in it.

Logan a Secondary 2 (S3) student March 2020 N5

Being creative and imaginative like in English (MAYBE consider creative writing in art) Ye I think so.

I think I have the language to describe

How to design things better

Designing clothing around a theme of our choice.

Cutting them out was difficult

Douglas a Secondary 4 (S4) student March 2020 N5

Early interview – **time was the most difficult aspect of the making**

Scales and layers

Paper samples (least difficult)

You have to think of everything (creativity)

Expand ones view of things

Teachers are passionate

You would understand your work better when you write about it.

To speak is to understand.

Second interview – **very clear process**

Time involved remains the most difficult aspect

Intricacy and precision - a valued skill

Attention to detail – this is an aspect which has helped in other subjects like English –

looking at things in more depth and with more care.

Notes: mainly photographic and verbal (not written)

Sitting the theory paper

I struggled with the language because it wasn't my own work it wasn't personal to me.

I see (observation) I think (personal view), because (general justification)

Final interview

Painting takes a lot of time.

Dedication of time (this is what time looks like)

Questions following the re-presentation of the data in the form of concept visualisations (assemblage)

2.0 How do you think the visualisation has captured your understanding of your learning?

It layers the learning and I can read and understand it.

2.1 How do you think the visualisation has captured our conversation?

I can imagine this in an exhibition

I can see the development of the art and the development of final products and me explaining it.

They would be able to work out the process.

Were you thinking that the image of the trophy matches the idea of being a perfectionist, that's a good point, it had the symmetry so it worked in unifying the overall image.

2.3 Is there a place for concept visualisation in art learning?

It makes me stop and pause.

Taking me back to the days when I was making the art. The layers of the text and the art symbolises the layers in the design for example.

Amira a Secondary 4 (S4) student March 2020 N5

1.0 Can you describe what you are doing right now?

I am currently doing National 5 art and design and I'm doing expressive right now. I'm working up to creating my final piece which will be still life.

1.1 Can you talk me through your process of your art-making? (have you made this?)

So this is a single object - this is a polaroid camera what is my theme is my favourite things. So, I have collated some of my favourite things relating to what I'm doing. and so, I really like photography. And my camera is my project. And how have you made this picture? Generally when I start drawing I like to split my picture into four sections and I work in sections. Is there an original photograph that replicates this? So, you chose to isolate the rest of it and cut out this? So, the picture was taken of the single object.

1.2 What was the most difficult aspect of your making?

I think making it the same shape ... are

1.3 What was the least difficult aspect?

Probably adding the tone.

1.4 What do you hope to learn by making this? (What is the range of knowledge and skills in arts-practice?)

And maybe further improve my tonal pencil skills.

Questions following the re-presentation of the data in the form of concept visualisations (assemblage)

2.0 How do you think the visualisation has captured your understanding of your learning?

It layers the learning and I can read and understand it.

2.1 How do you think the visualisation has captured our conversation?

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2.3 Is there a place for concept visualisation in art learning?

It makes me stop and pause.

Taking me back to the days when I was making the art. The layers of the text and the art symbolises the layers in the design for example.

1.0 Can you describe what you are doing right now?

In the drawings? Yes,

Aaam well right now this one is a flute, aa it's taking a lot of time because of there is a lot of reflections and I recently did this candle about a week ago [amm] this wasn't an image, this was placed in front of me amm and that one I think I did a lot more quickly, this one I'm taking a lot more time on focussing on every single detail, because it is a lot more intricate

Is this your flute ?

Aa this is just a flute that ... it's not mine, it's taken from the music department and I have just taken a photo of it.

Can you play it?

No I don't play an instrument.

1.1 Can you talk me through your process of your art-making? (How have you made this?)

Amm well I think the flute I was kinda just...it was quite difficult to start off with it looked like it was so confusing I didn't know what was going on

I don't play the flute.

So I just started from one end and just like slowly making my way up and every like analysing every single...every single area and the tone of the area and the different colours aam because the reflections are very very complicated and I think am it's quite difficult to aaam do it in one whole thing so I am taking very small bits and doing at a time.

I think the candle is quite different the candle it is more like one steady tone it a lot quicker and a lot easier.

1.2 What was the most difficult aspect of your making?

Aaam I think it was ...I think just the ...I think its quite difficult to like aam see all the reflections. Like when you look at them for a while. The more you look at them the less sense they seem to make.

So aam I think just the making it look exactly like the image was really difficult I think.

1.3 What was the least difficult aspect?

I think the simple geometric shapes is quite easy, the circle the lines because these are quite basic ...

1.4 What do you hope to learn by making this? (What is the range of knowledge and skills in arts-practice?)

Well, I think I really hope to just improve on my analytic skills of the picture as well as the variations in tone to emphasise like the different reflections in the flute and just generally improve my skill in pencil work.

1.5 What knowledge and skills do you hope to achieve?

Just the increased range of tone and the analysing the picture and applying what I see onto the page with accuracy.

1.6 What knowledge and skills are valued by you?

Well I think am well I think I struggled with separating the tones, it all kind of blends together. So I think the flute eh because it has a lot of light and darks and it really quite valuable to me helped me flesh out the different tones and improvement making

1.7 What knowledge and skills are valued by the school?

I think the School just it wants a degree of accuracy and also like the geometry to be quite... to visually represent the image through the tone and the shape and the line am yea and I think that's what the school would value.

1.8 Do you have the subject-specific language to enable you to verbally articulate your learning?

I think to an extent.

I know like words like tone line and shape mean in terms of art and in terms of drawing. But I feel like there is a bit of something I'm lacking in when talking about the art work.

What might that be?

I think amm more work specific art specific language that I'm struggling in.

I'm not quite sure what the language could be because I don't know.

WELL, THE LANGUAGE OF ART IS DIFFERENT FROM the language of OTHER SUBJECTS

Yes definitely, like line and shape those mean quite different things and tone Tone is all about the way the light has an effect on something whilst tone in other subjects is like the feeling, the mood and art I feel I picked up language in the subject but I haven't quite added to my vocabulary so there is stuff I haven't picked up on. Well we can come back to that later.

1.9 Do learners need to be able to describe their learning (in verbal and written modes) and if so what are the benefits?

I think it's good to be able to get a point across in a clear way although not necessary through verbal/and articulation ... my teacher (Ms H) could be telling to apply about applying more shade in more areas but its not until I see her do it that so I understand.

Engaging in conversation can really help you understand and where you need to improve and what skill you need to develop

So that is the verbal, what about the written ...talking about

Yea I think its yeah I think it's good to get across what you mean but I think it's a lot easier when you have like subject specific language. And you can really struggle to find the words. I think in written work I think it important to describe it. If your talking about exams. It's much easier ...

What are you learning?

I think I'm learning apart from I think I think in terms of

A skill is a lot more Attention to detail

That is something I've noticed

I'll look like a bottle

And you can see the When you have more attention to detail...

It easy to look at an object

This one I'm taking more time on

*I was kinda of
It was quite difficult to start with was so confusing
I hope to improve on my analytic skills, increased range of tone
I struggled with the tone*

What does the school want?

It wants a degree of accuracy and also the geometry to represent the image and

*To an extent I have the language
Lacking to be able to fluidly...*

I don't play an instrument

*Process of making
Analysing every single
Very small bits*

*Simple geometric shapes
I hope to improve
Applying what I see*

*To an extent
I'm lacking, more words specific, art specific, I'm not sure what the language would
be,
Tone – is all about light*

I think it is good to be able to a point across in a clear way

*It is not until I see her doing it do I fully understand
Generally
What is it your are you learning?
Applying what I see on to the page with accuracy
A lot more attention to detail – this is something you would only.*

Do learners need to be able describe

*It is not until I see her doing that I understand
Really struggle to find the words.*

I think I'm learning.

Questions following the re-presentation of the data in the form of concept visualisations (assemblage)

2.0 How do you think the visualisation has captured your understanding of your learning?

The first thing that jumps out at me is the idea of straying from the image. It a good way of conveying a quick point. With the collage you can see progression. The more you look into it you can see the conversation in the background. The main points are very visible – the context is visible. It gives context to the words

It definitely true – the work ethic is valued

You could have all the talent in the world but if you didn't have the work ethic you wouldn't get it done. It highlights the main take away

Attention to detail and work ethic.

It was not important to make the perfect picture

As you look closer you

It looks like how I might have left out my art to be looked at!

As an image that displays my learning in art it definitely shows that!

It makes it more interesting.

2.1 How do you think the visualisation has captured our conversation?

2.3 Is there a place for concept visualisation in art learning?

Yes, its intriguing.

1.0 Can you describe what you are doing right now?

So I 'm making a headpiece for design. So kind of based around sleeping beauty so the kind of spirally what's it called the spindle wheel sewing wheel and kind of flowers that go with that. And feathers screws and stuff lots of lots of pink that fits into that but make it look like a headpiece... we've done tracings kind of followed it and copied it. There is meant to be symmetry in then do a structural piece. [are these words? It looks like it.]

So this is the beginning of what?

So, this is just development want to make a big... with the spirals I've got wee beads which I'll add onto the headpiece.

So how long is it taking you to do this?

These took two periods which is an hour and 40 minutes.

1.1 Can you talk me through your process of your art-making? (How have you made this?)

So we start off with pictures we've got off the Internet and pinterest. So I've got pictures of flowers things like that and to draw the out of the full piece of paper...

1.2 What was the most difficult aspect of your making?

So trying to make them look as lifelike as possible so things all matchup, so I don't want to looking all cartoony. So, I quite like stuff when it looks realistic

1.3 What was the least difficult aspect?

The colouring in so once you've drawn all out it's quite therapeutic, I've not had to think too hard about it. So, I just picked for different colours.

1.4 What do you hope to learn by making this? (What is the range of knowledge and skills in arts-practice?)

1.5 What knowledge and skills do you hope to achieve?

Don't quite like to see something really nice at the end I want to look well put together I don't I how to explain it I'd like to show the pictures and say where that came from...

1.6 What knowledge and skills are valued by you?

I don't know. Knowing that different things can come from different places

1.7 What knowledge and skills are valued by the school?

I'm not sure honestly. Timekeeping and being able to do something in the time given. Making it look really nice and not rushing out.

1.8 Do you have the subject-specific language to enable you to verbally articulate your learning?

I am not very good is saying what I'm doing not very good at articulating it. I don't know why we doing some things at times.

I know it's self-development and stuff I don't just don't know what the language would be.

1.9 Do learners need to be able to describe their learning (in verbal and written modes) and if so what are the benefits?

It makes you understand it better if you're able to say. Like in history if your topic you don't know what are you doing it's you will be able to understand it.

Questions following the re-presentation of the data in the form of concept visualisations (assemblage)

2.0 How do you think the visualisation has captured your understanding of your learning?

I recognise the things I said...

It looks a bit all over the place the things I was saying...

Well not really if you look at what others said...

What I have been doing is producing an artwork that reflects some of the issues about art learning if you like

It's a complex image and it takes a while to take in, [yes it does]

I've produced these in A3 and I've been staring at these for months

The intention was to bring image and text a bit closer and to consolidate your learning

I've pushed some of the conversation into the background.

if you go back over the origins of the questions I askedtalking through the process, the difficult aspects, the range of knowledge and skills]

I think it shows that its hard to pin point an exact, like there is not like an end point but everything came together in the end

Yes that what the image is meant to conveys and I think if you isolate some of the things you said they are quite profound such as...if you are able to describe your learning you are able to understand it.

You very identified the 'not knowing' in the sense I have a bit of language but I don't know why because all of this have been privileged over and above everything else.

Joe a Secondary 6 (S6) student March 2020 Higher

1.0 Can you describe what you are doing right now?

Well, I'm just trying to experiment using different techniques and different materials to like express natural forms and artists images in different ways using sticks of graphite or chalk or Biro Pen or whatever I can find I can use.

1.1 Can you talk me through your process of your art-making? How have you made this?

The first thing I did was get the such as scaffolding. My first thought was to do linear architecture what I thought the scaffolding was a bit more interesting you could see the shadows so using like the graphite and the oil pastels and techniques you could just experiment how to reiterated how do you feel so on the second page is an artist image to link it together so for this one I did the same thing but just put this on top just like to join them together and using the wire rods as well just to show the lines made here just introduced a bit of colour red as well

So why the colour?

Just add a bit more life to it rather than it's just being all monochromatic black-and-white.

1.2 What was the most difficult aspect of your making?

I think are trying to use different materials and different ways of copying the image kind of it takes a wee while to think about what you need to do these two pages took me I think three periods to do that's 100 hundred and fifty minutes. So it's a lot of time thinking about it.

Is that all school-based time?

Yes it's all school-based time, you can take it away but it's all school-based right now. I'll take it away in the future.

1.3 What was the least difficult aspect?

You see finding the images I had already vision of what I want to do quite fast so finding the easy the images was the easiest. So it still quite tight we spent a week or two on the computers trying to find images that we want to use all we think will be successful

1.4 What do you hope to learn by making this? (What is the range of knowledge and skills in arts-practice?)

This stuff I'm learning is not really art-based but I'm thinking it is more learning outside the box in different situations and applying different things whatever you come across

1.5 What knowledge and skills do you hope to achieve?

A lot of advanced higher is just experimenting if something goes wrong just try again are just putting on your page to show you've tried something but you don't think it's the best just like trying stuff again if you feel it's not good enough or to the Stonely job it can still be put down on the page.

1.6 What knowledge and skills are valued by you?

I would say confidence has a lot to do with advanced higher if you are like wary of putting something down on the page are you might so it's really what your thoughts are that is going onto the page how you see different things

1.7 What knowledge and skills are valued by the school?

I think it's just trying to respect your work is a big part of it rather than getting rid of everything you think is not the best you're often be told it is good even though not down on yourself just go to got instant even if it is not the best.

I think it's very unique around the school as well

1.8 Do you have the subject-specific language to enable you to verbally articulate your learning?

I think I could talk about but maybe not perfectly but there is always learning to do I think. If you Wanna talk about your work you need to understand what you're doing and why I think

1.9 Do learners need to be able to describe their learning (in verbal and written modes) and if so what are the benefits?

I think in some form you should be able to articulate what you doing

I think a lot of my work is to do with what I think on the spot hi just go for that I don't really think anything else when I'm doing the artwork I think it's a good idea so I just go ahead with it and sometimes I don't understand and sometimes I can articulate what I'm doing but I just do it anyway.

I think not all the time do you know why you're doing something what you going to get out of it you do it anyway.

You do it because you're obviously getting some encouragement

Teachers encourage you to not just think about whether it's good enough encourage you to use different materials different things maybe not just in art maybe just life in general I think that could be giving us a lesson in how to live and not just in art. In the future I was thinking of doing like photography thinking of doing stuff with my photography and then applying it to art as well. So I could even go and take some photographs of the scaffolding.

1.0 Can you describe what you are doing right now?

Amm well in Advanced Higher art, we're choosing a certain... well I'm doing architecture so I'm choosing buildings and I've kinda went down the realms of New Orleans and those type of buildings and will choose those subject matters and we'll say use charcoal and do different drawings of them and then maybe move on to different pens or aam aam like other structures of these buildings and archways and stuff like that and aaa creating a big folio basically in these sketchbooks it then gets sent away to prove how we've got to our final boards and stuff.

1.1 Can you talk me through your process of your art-making? (How have you made this?)

It might be useful for you to see something.

Okay I'll go and get it.

Brilliant excellent

quite big books that we're working with

This will really help us I feel

Amm So we'll go online and we'll maybe go onto pinstrest or something like that and we'll find... see like that is basic New Orleans kinda house to me is what I think of so we'll kinda of draw like what I have done with ink there, pencil and pencil again and these are all just mark makings to describe an archway

Amm So it's just kind of like picking an image from online and seeing what we can create out of that one image and then there was like this one. I kind of focused more on this part of the building and I extended some about me bigger versions of it and that was charcoal some of the structures that I've seen here ari and stuff like that this was a printmaking stage to be done as well so we chose laminate take up these little like blades they have big handles and stuff for them so you could kind of carve it out and you put ink over it and press it on different things like Polystyrene

And we were like carving into that and doing loads of printmaking

It was just kind of like choosing an image and seeing what we can create from it and zooming in on certain aspects of the image and stuff like that

1.2 What was the most difficult aspect of your making?

I think trying to keep all your work consistent...

So I think on this page this was one of my best drawings

And then I don't really like these ones I've Done that with pen that was charcoal and that was pencil

So I think with that image pen would be better

If you know what I mean trying to keep your all of your work in a consistent level I think is the hardest part of it

your mistakes are good in art are always good I guess in art

They're always good to see

you've got to certain images and stuff like that.

1.3 What was the least difficult aspect?

Amm I think once I've got once I've got an image that I've printed off and have stuck into my book I think the easiest part for me is like what I'll do first how I

think it's just like what I will do first so when I printed that off first basically the same image that's obviously me drawing in pen I'm from that it was like what else can I draw that I think it's quite easy to go through different like techniques and stuff going through a full pension stuff and I find it easy to get a full-page done within half an hour sometimes

1.4 What do you hope to learn by making this? (What is the range of knowledge and skills in arts-practice?)

I think it shows with these sketchbooks that your mistakes aren't the worst thing in life I think that what it shows see look at this I think here my shadows in this the worst thing but then my teachers say I know but so I like it been quite messy making a mistake is sometimes really good and it's not always a bad thing to make mistakes shows what it's like in life as well it shows with these sketchbooks that your mistakes aren't the worst thing.

1.5 What knowledge and skills do you hope to achieve?

*I don't really know with art especially, you don't really know (not in a bad way) you don't really know what you are doing until it's achieved
You don't know what you are doing until it is achieved, I'm just taking pictures at the moment. And I would say to the teacher what am I doing next and she would say just keep going you'll figure it out – you know what I mean. So I think I don't know really... I really don't know.*

1.6 What knowledge and skills are valued by you?

*I don't know really, amm I just think you know what you are doing when you come in to art and I'll figure out this is what I'm going to do today. right that's very good that's what I'm going to do, sometimes I'll do something very quickly
To keep this page quite messy
That's just a good way to be within art
Just coming into it you don't really need to know exactly what you're doing
And I think you can just continue on from there.*

1.7 What knowledge and skills are valued by the school?

*Amm I think the school, I think with National 5 and Higher Art I think it's all very structured to this first and do this and do this
and I quite like I quite like that you're just there scribbling over a page making art and I think that's what art is it's not very structured that's why I like how really do within the art department it's very you do what you think.*

*I think the school needs to realise this is how art is made
And still do not know What I'm going to do for my final but it's just that way of getting yourself in that mindset do you know that I mean*

1.8 Do you have the subject-specific language to enable you to verbally articulate your learning?

*I don't really know (what do you mean?) a language that is associated with art.
I'm doing maths right now and with maths you your going with the formulas. In art you are very free and with maths you can't be free
because you are going with the rules of maths*

In art you are very free it's okay to have mistakes it's like to be okay with messiness and stuff in English you need to be a very particular with your work very neat and very to the rules and that's why I like art so much you come in is just like on you go go and find things and go and make art

1.9 Do learners need to be able to describe their learning (in verbal and written modes) and if so what are the benefits?

Wait and see how I could describe art too people

See when I'm talking to my parents about art I don't

I feel it is very hard to describe art because no one can get into your head even teachers!

Questions following the re-presentation of the data in the form of concept visualisations (assemblage)

2.1 How do you think the visualisation has captured our conversation?

Yes, definitely I think it does but looking back at it now I think it was a lot more structured like now doing advanced higher I'm working in free rein.

2.3 Is there a place for concept visualisation in art learning?

It highlights the bits you could be confused about how there is not always a right way to go about those things it just effort and time and making a small plan though it kinda of shows you can't, it shows the method is all over the place and at the same time it comes together. it's like a single consolidated image of your learning

Looking back at it now, it was a lot more structured compared to now. It definitely shows that I took a lot of time

Appendix 4

Diarmuid McAuliffe
Lecturer in Art Education
School of Education
University of the West of Scotland
University Avenue
Ayr, KA8 0SX

12 April 2018

[REDACTED]

Dear [REDACTED]

I am Subject Lead for Art Teacher Education at the School of Education, University of the West of Scotland. I am also undertaking the Professional Doctorate, and it is in this capacity that I write formally to request your permission to carry out a small-scale 'pupil articulation' research project in the Art Department [REDACTED]

The working title for the project is ***Using narrative and arts-based methods to make visible (draw out) learning in secondary art education.***

I have made an informal approach to the headteacher [REDACTED] and the Principal Teacher of Art, [REDACTED] and both are very supportive of the project. They consider that it has the potential to inform their work and to improve outcomes for pupils in relation to 'pupil articulation' in art education.

I anticipate that I will need to be at the school a day a week for between 6-12 months, beginning shortly after the Easter break (April 2018). The purpose is to observe and work alongside a number of small groups of pupils (3-4) over this 6-12 month period. The project will involve observing and working with no more than fourteen pupils in total, drawn from across S1-S6. Pupils will be selected in consultation with [REDACTED] and access will be negotiated in accordance with the university's guidelines for the conduct of ethical research.

I will be involving the learners in a number of conversations through the medium of semi-structured interviews around their art making and learning. These will be conducted within the open-plan area of the department. I will develop a series of Case study Assemblages based on these interviews. Pupils will be given the opportunity to check for accuracy and understanding.

If you require any further information or wish to seek clarity on any aspect of the project, please do not hesitate to contact me.

[REDACTED]

Personal details withheld.

Diarmuid McAuliffe
Lecturer in Art Education
School of Education
University of the West of Scotland
University Avenue, Ayr, KA8 0SX

12 April 2018

[REDACTED]

Dear [REDACTED]

I am Subject Lead for Art Teacher Education at the School of Education, University of the West of Scotland. I am also undertaking the Professional Doctorate, and it is in this capacity that I now write formally to request your permission to carry out a small-scale 'pupil articulation' research project in the Art Department at [REDACTED]. The project, has just today been granted ethical approval by our Research Ethics Committee at UWS; this will explain my delay in getting this formal request to you.

The working title for the project is ***Using narrative and arts-based methods to make visible (draw out) learning in secondary art education.***

As you are already aware I have made an informal approach to the Principal Teacher of Art, [REDACTED] who is very supportive of the project. [REDACTED] her staff recognise that the project has the potential to inform their work and to improve outcomes for pupils in relation to 'pupil articulation' in art education. I have also written to [REDACTED], The Director of Education to inform her of the project.

I anticipate that I will need to be at the school a day a week for between 6-12 months, beginning shortly after the Easter break (April 2018). The purpose is to observe and work alongside a number of small groups of pupils (3-4) over this 6-12 month period. The project will involve observing and working with no more than fourteen pupils in total, drawn from across S1-S6. Pupils will be selected in consultation with yourself and [REDACTED] and access will be negotiated in accordance with the university's guidelines for the conduct of ethical research.

I will be involving the learners in a number of conversations through the medium of semi-structured interviews around their art making and learning. These will be conducted within the open-plan area of the department. I will develop a series of Case study Assemblages based on these interviews. Pupils will be given the opportunity to check for accuracy and understanding.

If you require any further information or wish to seek clarity on any aspect of the project,

[REDACTED]

Personal details withheld.

Appendix 5

Informed Consent Form

Project title: Using narrative and arts-based methods to make visible (draw out) learning in secondary art education.

- I have read and understood the Participant Information Sheet;
- I have been given the opportunity to ask questions and have had them answered to my satisfaction;
- I agree to take part in this project; I understand that my participation is voluntary and that I am free to withdraw at any time up until the beginning of data analysis;
- I consent to the procedures for handling any personal data collected (e.g. confidentiality, anonymisation will be guaranteed);
- I consent to proposals for data storage, archiving, sharing and re-use for future research, exhibition and publication;
- I consent to the planned audio recording of learner conversations and to the capture of still visual images of artwork that result from the data collection and transcription process. No video recording will take place.

Appendix 6

Participant Information Sheet (CHILD)

Title of Project: *Using narrative and arts-based methods to make visible (draw out) learning in secondary art education*

The sponsoring institution is the University of the West of Scotland

This research is reviewed by my supervisors (Dr Anne Pirrie and Dr Stephen Day) and is assessed separately for ethical approval by the University's Ethics Committee.

The purpose of the research is to find out through a process of articulation (using narrative and arts-based methods) what learners learn in the art class and how they articulate and understand that learning.

Participants will engage with the researcher in a number of learner conversations around their art making. No more than 14 participants will be involved in the research.

The benefits and disadvantages/risks of participation. The benefits of taking part in this research are, that participants may increase their level of verbal and written articulation around their art making and learning. There are no known risks to the participants.

Participation in this research is entirely voluntary and participants can withdraw from the project at any time up to the beginning of data analysis.

What will happen to the data? All data, visual (drawings and artworks) and voice recordings will be anonymised and held by the researcher in a secure location at the University. Confidentiality will be maintained throughout the period of research and only with the expressed permission of the participant will any of the data be made public.

How results will be disseminated? The results will be made available through a series of Case study Assemblages via exhibition and writings (academic papers) in the form of a dissertation

Further information.

If you require any further information or wish to seek clarity on any aspect of the project, please, do not hesitate to contact me:

Personal details withheld.

Participant Information Sheet (Adult)

Title of Project: Using narrative and arts-based methods to make visible (draw out) learning in secondary art education

The sponsoring institution is the University of the West of Scotland

This research is reviewed by my supervisors (Dr Anne Pirrie and Dr Stephen Day) and is assessed separately for ethical approval by the University's Ethics Committee.

The purpose of the research is to find out through a process of articulation (using narrative and arts-based methods) what learners learn in the art class and how they articulate and understand that learning.

Participants will engage with the researcher in a number of learner conversations around their art making. No more than 14 participants will be involved in the research.

The benefits and disadvantages/risks of participation. The benefits of taking part in this research are, that participants may increase their level of verbal and written articulation around their art-making and learning. There are no known risks to the participants.

Participation in this research is entirely voluntary and participants can withdraw from the project at any time up to the beginning of data analysis.

What will happen to the data? All data, visual (drawings and artworks) and voice recordings will be anonymised and held by the researcher in a secure location at the University. Confidentiality will be maintained throughout the period of research and only with the expressed permission of the participant will any of the data be made public.

How results will be disseminated? The results will be made available through a series of Case study Assemblages via exhibition and writings (academic papers) in the form of a dissertation

Further information.

If you require any further information or wish to seek clarity on any aspect of the project, please, do not hesitate to contact me:

Personal details withheld.

Everyday Fragments on the Ceiling of Room 407: An Open Narrative Inquiry Space. In Kirkpatrick, D, Porter, S, Speedy, J and Wyatt J (2021). Permission granted to reproduce these pages.

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From Everyday Fragments on the Ceiling of Room 407: An Open Narrative Inquiry Space. In Kirkpatrick, D, Porter, S, Speedy, J and Wyatt J (2021).

Riffing off Tami: Tami Spry's Performative Call and Collaborative Response.
 In Kirkpatrick, D, Porter, S, Speedy, J and Wyatt J (2021: 103).

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Appendix 8

Examples of Concept Visualisations

Rollins, T (2012) Study for A Midsummer Night's Dream (After William Shakespeare) 2011, Watercolour and offset lithograph on paper. In Rollins, T (2012) *Tim Rollins and K.O.S.: An Index*. Zurich: JRP/Ringier

Rollins, T (2012) *Paradiso (After Dante) 2003*, Watercolour on book paper. In Rollins, T (2012) *Tim Rollins and K.O.S.: An Index*. Zurich: JRP/Ringier

Appendix 9

Self-Portrait, Gillard (2018)

In the next three works of art I explore a triptych that incorporates my poetry nested between two images that express my liminal, 'ma' 間.

Figure 2. *Self-portrait (1)*, 2010, Installation.¹

¹ Presented at art events: "ART" and Caught in the Middle, AMS Gallery UBC, 2010.

Self-

sunlight slips into blinked eyes
capture my sense of existence
I hide behind the light

my sense of existence
stays in daily momentum
a reciprocated world

the corner of the gallery full of
Duchamp
allows me to speak out loud

an ironing board full of concepts
burning sent on my white shirts
stays forever or not

a letter 'A', a symbol appears

I take my hats off to rest my mind
so as my sun umbrella protects me

I see my future in a frame
hiding a water jug

It is empty

nothing exists quite the same
without the sun
creation of grays, we command

inside out of the gallery space
domestically placed in the center
of attention

I am an imaginator

Self-portrait
my sense of belonging in the world
with the light created
by the shadows
in my liminal space

Gillard, Y (2018) Beginning in the middle: my liminal space of 'MA'. In Sinner, A; Irwin, R. L and Jokela, T. (Eds.) *Visually Provoking: Dissertations in Art Education*. Rovaniemi: Lapland University Press. The University of British Columbia :140

Appendix 10 Observation and interview timetable at the Research School

			Class	Days in	Teacher	Notes: Commence 12 November; (12 weeks) Next rotation 18 February
S1	F		1ML	Monday		* * *
Participant 1						
Participant 2	F		1ML	Monday		* * *
Participant 3	M		1ML	Monday		* * *
<hr/>						
S2	F		2GH	Friday		***
participant 4b						
Participant 5b	M		2GH	Friday		**
Participant 6b	M		2GH	Friday		***
<hr/>						
S3 participant 7	(M)		3.8	Wed and Thurs		* * SEEN S3 FINAL WORK
participant 8	(F)		3.7	Wed and Thurs		* *
<hr/>						
S4 National 5	(M)		4.6	Thurs and Fri		* * SEEN N5 FINAL WORK
Participant 10	(F)		4.2	Thurs and Fri		* * SEEN N5 FINAL WORK
<hr/>						
S5 Higher 11	(M)		5.1	Fri		* * * * SEEN HIGHER FINAL WORK
Participant 12	(F)		5.2	Fri		* * * * SEEN HIGHER FINAL WORK
<hr/>						
S6 Advanced Higher 13	(M)		6.2	Fri		* * * * speak to him after Higher photography exam DATE?
Participant 14	(F)		6.1 D	Fri Thur		* * * * SEEN ADVANCED HIGHER FINAL WORK

Personal details withheld.

Appendix 11

Whiteboard thinking: Initial 'thinking out of the project at the University of Bristol (2018)

